

PROBONO

D9.1 Market Analysis

PROBONO - The Integrator-centric approach for realising innovative energy efficient buildings in connected sustainable green neighbourhoods - has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101037075. This output reflects only the author's view, and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Deliverable nº:	D9.1
Deliverable name:	Market Analysis
Version:	1.0
Release date:	22/12/2023
Dissemination level:	Public
Status:	Final
Authors:	Smart Innovation Norway (SIN)

Document history:

Version	Date of issue	Content and changes	Edited by
0.1	30/06/2023	Table of contents (ToC)	Alemu Belay (SIN), Dimitris Rizopoulos (INLE), María Jiménez (PNO), Edgar Valverde (PNO), Aaditya Dandwate (SIN)
0.2	31/10/2023	50% complete version	Ahmed Samir Hedar (SIN), Aaditya Dandwate (SIN), Dimitris Rizopoulos (INLE), María Jiménez (PNO), Edgar Valverde (PNO), Alemu Belay (SIN)
0.3	05/12/2023	100% complete version for review	Ahmed Samir Hedar (SIN), Aaditya Dandwate (SIN), Dimitris Rizopoulos (INLE), María Jiménez (PNO), Edgar Valverde (PNO), Alemu Belay (SIN)
1.0	22/12/2023	Final version (Peer-reviewed)	Ahmed Samir Hedar (SIN), Aaditya Dandwate (SIN), Dimitris Rizopoulos (INLE), María Jiménez (PNO), Edgar Valverde (PNO), Alemu Belay (SIN)

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Deliverable beneficiaries:

WP / Task
WP9/T9.1

DEFINITIONS¹

A Green Building (GB) (new or retrofit) is a building that, in its design, construction and operation, reduces or eliminates negative impacts, and can create positive impacts, on the climate, social, and natural environment. GBs preserve precious natural resources and improve quality of life². Specifically, this means that GBs should be very energy efficient, use extensively the potential of locally available renewable energy, use sustainable materials, and aim for a low environmental impact over the entire life cycle. GBs offer their users and residents a healthy climate and a high quality of stay, they are resilient e.g., to environmental change and contribute to social inclusion.

Green Neighbourhoods aligned with the European Green Deal³, is a set of buildings over a delimited area, at a scale that is smaller than a district, with potential synergies, in particular in the area of energy. A green neighbourhood is a neighbourhood that allows for environmentally friendly, sustainable patterns and behaviours to flourish e.g., bioclimatic architecture, renewable energy, soft and zero-emission

¹ Please refer to the last submitted reports for the latest status of the definitions

² <https://www.worldgbc.org/what-green-building>

³ European_Green_Deal_EN_200710_fin

mobility etc. Green neighbourhoods are the building blocks of Positive Energy Districts (PEDs)⁴ by implementing key elements of PED energy systems. For example, the exchange of energy between buildings increases the share of local self-supply with climate-neutral energy and system efficiency. They also provide the technical conditions to enable Citizen Energy Communities⁵ and Renewable Energy Communities⁶ to be implemented.

Green Buildings and Neighbourhoods (GBN) in PROBONO are GBs integrated at a delimited area or district level with green energy and green mobility management and appropriate infrastructure supported by policies, investments and stakeholders' engagement and behaviours that ensure just transition that maximise the economic and social co-benefits considering a district profile (population size, socio-economic structure, and geographical and climate characteristics). Delivered in the right way, GBN infrastructure is a key enabler of inclusive growth, can improve the accessibility of housing and amenities, reduce poverty and inequality, widen access to jobs and education, make communities more resilient to climate change, and promote public health and wellbeing.

DGNB certification serves as a quality stamp ensuring the state of the building for buyers. The Green Building Council Denmark (2010) established the German certification DGNB meaning 'German Society for Sustainable Buildings'. The Danish version of DGNB was created to obtain a common definition of what sustainability is towards and making it measurable. A consortium of experts was established from all parts of the construction sector. DGNB had to be reshaped for the Danish standards, practice, traditions, and laws but is now available to certify any construction project. They chose DGNB as an innovation-forward and sustainable futures guarantee. DGNB diversifies itself by focusing on sustainability and not just the environment. DGNB creates a standardised framework for the construction operations conditions and creates a common language which facilitates communication between professions and helps organize and prioritize the efforts in long and complicated development phases.

Life cycle assessment (LCA)⁷ is a tool used for the systematic quantitative assessment of each material used, energy flows and environmental impacts of products or processes. LCA assesses various aspects associated with development of a product and its potential impact throughout a product's life (i.e., cradle to grave) from raw material acquisition, processing, manufacturing, use and finally its disposal. In PROBONO, LCA represents the statement of a building's total energy, resource consumption and environmental impact in the manufacture, transport, and replacement of materials and for its operation over its expected life. Social life cycle assessment (S-LCA)⁸ is a method to assess the social and sociological aspects of products, their actual and potential positive as well as negative impacts along the life cycle. Life-cycle costing (LCC)⁹ considers all the costs incurred during the lifetime of the product, work, or service.

⁴ SET-Plan Action 3.2: https://setis.ec.europa.eu/system/files/setplan_smartcities_implementationplan.pdf

⁵ Internal Electricity Market Directive (EU) 2019/944 5 Renewable Energy Directive (EU)

⁶ Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/20012018/2001

⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/16cd2d1d-2216-11e8-ac73-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

⁸ <https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/starting-life-cycle-thinking/life-cycle-approaches/social-lca/>

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/lcc.htm>

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AHU	Air Handling Unit
AR	Augmented Reality
BEM	Building Energy Modelling
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BIPV	Building Integrated Photovoltaic
BTU	British Thermal Units
CAGR	Compounded Annual Growth Rate
CSP	Concentrated Solar (thermal) Power
DT	Digital Twins
EMS	Energy Management Systems
EV	Electric Vehicles
GBN	Green Buildings and Neighbourhoods
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
GWP	Global Warming Potential
HP	Heat Pump
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
IC	Innovation Cluster
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KIR	Key Innovative Result
LCA	Life Cycle Analysis
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Electricity
LCOH	Levelized Cost of Heating
LCOS	Levelized Cost of Storage
LL	Living Lab
PED	Positive Energy District
PEN	Positive Energy Neighbourhood
PESTEL	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal
PV	Photovoltaic
ROI	Return On Investment
SPEN	Sustainable Plus Energy Neighbourhood
TES	Thermal Energy Storage
V2G	Vehicle to grid
VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work package

Executive summary

The deliverable D9.1 (Market Analysis) is part of the PROBONO Work Package 9 (Replicability, Exploitation and Commercialisation) and Task 9.1 (PROBONO Technologies: Market Analysis). This report focuses on the market analysis for the PROBONO's GBN technologies and/or solutions relevant for the Green Buildings and Neighbourhoods (GBN) concept. The key aspects of this deliverable include-

- Market segmentation based on technology for the GBN solutions, to analyse macro-level categorisation of the technologies and solutions
- Identification of market indicators (techno-economic, social, environmental) for the segments of GBN solutions
- Market needs validation for analysing sustainability of GBNs and future customers/end-users of the PROBONO results
- Innovation potential to the market for GBN solutions including factors such as barriers and influences of market scenarios

The aim of this report was to analyse the current and future market scenarios and its relation to the PROBONO projects GBN solutions. The results and outcomes of the market analysis in this report shall be used as inputs and reference for the exploitation and replication activities of WP9 in the PROBONO project. The outcomes of this market analysis shall also serve as inputs and discussion points for the living labs and other project partners who are implementing the GBN technologies and/or solutions in the PROBONO project. Furthermore, this work shall further be fine-tuned and revised based on the requirements of the WP9 task (T9.1 and T9.2) activities and shall be used as inputs for the other deliverables in WP9 to cater to the specific GBN technologies and/or solutions during the implementation phase of the project.

1 Introduction

1.1 Mapping PROBONO Outputs

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
Task 9.1 PROBONO Technologies: Market Analysis (M1-M60)	<p>This task underpins the project’s business models and commercialisation strategies with a detailed market analyses principally pivoted around the commercial ambitions of the project’s living labs.</p> <p>ST9.1.1 Market Indicators</p> <p>Gather techno-economic, socio-economic and sustainability indicators through a quantitative and qualitative assessment that looks into the size of the respective markets both in terms of volume and in value, commercial potential, licencing potential, the associated customer segments and buying patterns, the global competition and competitive landscape, and the economic environment in terms of barriers to entry and regulatory imperatives whilst factoring in health, safety, socio-economic and environmental dimensions.</p> <p>ST9.1.2 Market Segmentation</p> <p>Consider the potential development of market segments associated with the adoption of PROBONO tools and services by Utilities managers, and Construction companies, as well as the market segments for innovative energy and construction technology providers.</p> <p>ST9.1.3 Innovation Potential to Market</p> <p>Define and align PROBONO’s innovation to the target market segments based on clearly defined customer driven needs. Apply international best practises for Customer Discovery encompassing tools like Osterwalder Value Proposition Canvas, Customer Journey Maps plus PESTLE and SWOT Analysis to align and validate PROBONO’s outputs with specific and opportunistic customer segments.</p> <p>ST9.1.4 Market Needs Validation</p> <p>Market needs validated and informed by key representatives selected and onboarded in PROBONO’s planned Innovation Cluster. Identify strategic patents to ensure and achieve a commercial and competitive advantage underpinned by formal patent protection in targeted regions such as EU, USA and Canada, and the potential for incentivising additional commercial revenues.</p>	Chapters 2-7 and Annex 1	<p>This deliverable report caters to each of the subtasks in Task 9.1 to provide market analysis for the PROBONO’s GBN technologies/ solutions. This report will support the other activities and tasks in PROBONO’s WP9 (Replicability, Exploitation and Commercialisation) and for the duration of these activities as mentioned in DoA.</p>
DELIVERABLE			
<p>D9.1: Market Analysis This report formulates the findings of T9.1 and explores step(s) in the Market Analysis report.</p>			

Table 1: Adherence to PROBONO’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

1.2 Purpose and scope of the document

The purpose of this deliverable D9.1 'Market Analysis', is to provide a detailed market analysis that will support the exploitation and replication activities of WP9, and the living labs of the PROBONO project to facilitate their commercial ambitions during and after the completion of the PROBONO project. This deliverable provides an understanding and overview about the current and future market scenarios with respect to the technologies considered in the PROBONO project. The scope of market analysis in this deliverable incorporates the market trends, market segmentation based on technology, market indicators, stakeholder analysis and innovation potential of the GBN concept.

1.3 Structure of the document and its relationship with other WPS/Deliverables

The document consists of the following chapters:

- *Chapter 1: Introduction*, provides an overview about the structure of this deliverable and how it is related to the project
- *Chapter 2: Methodology*, provides an understanding about the sequence of information and content in this deliverable
- *Chapter 3: Market Segmentation of GBN Solutions*, provides an overview of segments for technological solutions that can be considered for GBNs
- *Chapter 4: Market Indicators for GBN Solutions*, provides the technical, economic, social and environmental indicators that help in understanding the market scenarios using quantitative and qualitative assessment
- *Chapter 5: Market Needs Validation towards GBN sustainability*, provides analysis to identify the stakeholders who can be either of end-users or clients of PROBONO's solutions
- *Chapter 6: PESTLE Analysis and Innovation Potential to Market*, provides a PESTLE analysis to understand the innovation potential of the PROBONO technologies or solutions
- *Chapter 7: Conclusion of Market Analysis*, summarises the market analysis, provides some key takeaways and establishes connection to future work.

1.4 Contribution to creating GBN

This deliverable provides an understanding and analysis about the market corresponding to the technologies and/or solutions considered in the PROBONO project for the Green Building Neighbourhoods (GBNs). As the GBN concept develops through the PROBONO project, it also becomes important to analyse the current and future market scenarios about the technologies and/or solutions used in the PROBONO for the development of the GBNs.

2 Methodology

This chapter gives an overview of a structured methodology for the market analysis of the PROBONO's GBN solutions implemented during the project execution and consider the exploitation potential of key exploitable results (KERs) of the project. The market analysis in this deliverable gives a macro-level understanding about the global and European level trends regarding the various GBN solutions including the market segmentation catering to concept of Green Building Neighbourhoods (GBNs) solutions, identifying and gathering the market indicators for the market segments based on technical, economic, social and environmental factors, analysis of the innovation potential of PROBONO's results and their relation to the current and future market scenarios. This deliverable also investigates the market-oriented stakeholder analysis that maps the potential end-users or customers for the PROBONO's GBN solutions and potential project exploitable results. The market analysis in this deliverable is supported by quantitative assessment using available and reliable databases, reports published by reputed organizations, research journals, literature data, surveys, etc., and qualitative assessment methods such as interviews, workshop results and meetings with the relevant project partners. This deliverable refers to other PROBONO deliverables already completed. In addition, some of the outcomes of this deliverable shall serve as inputs for Task 9.2 and upcoming deliverables D9.3 and D9.4 in the PROBONO project implementation timeline.

3 Market Segmentation of GBN solutions

Efforts under Task 9.1 and Subtask 9.1.2 of PROBONO's WP9 have been focused on deriving a market segmentation for the GBN domain according to the project's requirements and goals, as well as the global trends in the energy, construction, technological and scientific domains. The current market segmentation, as presented in this chapter, falls under the title of a value-based "GBN Solution Market Segmentation", that has been performed based on the expected solution preferences of GBN markets and respective customers. There are different types of market segmentation based on the types/maturity of technology (technography), geography, seasonal/environmental, economic, social (behavioural), etc. In this connection, the GBN solutions market segmentation have been grouped into eight technological categories that are relevant to PROBONO and normally met in literature (Figure 1).

The PROBONO technologies considered for this market segmentation come from the Key Exploitable Results list, as it has been collected early in the project by WP9 partners. These results have been grouped into several initial market segments in the first version of the market segmentation during the first year of PROBONO. The market segmentation and respective segments have been revised throughout duration of Task 9.1, mainly extending the segmentation to include more segments (as they currently are 8). The segments include at least all PROBONO technologies as they emerge in the project at the time of writing this deliverable report. In the attempt to provide a more holistic overview of the GBN-related market segments, even more solutions that are not directly included in the PROBONO pilots and Use Cases are considered in this chapter. The final number of market segments for this analysis has been finalized based on periodical feedback requests from WP9 (mainly task leaders PNO and SIN).

Figure 1: GBN solutions Market Segments

Complementary to the eight segments of Figure 1, and as discussed later in the report, an additional horizontal group of expected solutions of PROBONO is added that can help support the social dimension of adoption of GBNs (section 3.9), mainly including solutions that can contribute towards raising awareness, facilitating education and competency building, as well as further research in the field, after the lifetime of PROBONO.

In the bigger picture, a market segmentation analysis enables the writer and the reader to better define and understand target groups for a company's or an industry's products or services. In essence, the main goal is to specify groups of consumers so that specific products or services are directly targeted at them. To split up a market into segments, a marketer must identify key characteristics that distinguish the customer target groups from each other. As a result, marketing campaigns, product development, distribution channels, and other business functions can be optimized for a company's audience, in contrast to using generic approaches to reach potential customers. In the solutions segmentation that follows, a clear distinction between the different types of solutions that can comprise a GBN is shown. In that way, project partners can easily distinguish and, very importantly, position their project outcomes in the wider GBN market. This segmentation serves as a first step for project partner to identify potential customers and start their market analysis towards deploying a product or service to a market segment.

3.1 Renewable energy generation solutions

With improved efficiency, declining system costs, and reduced payback periods, renewables are becoming products of significant interest and investment prioritization for many households globally. This first segment of the green building solutions market are the renewable energy systems, whose products can provide a real alternative to grid-only electricity consumption or be used for heating or cooling purposes. Renewable energy sources are gaining momentum on a political level, with the EU's Renewable Energy Directive (2009/289/EC) currently setting the ambition of extracting 32% of the Union's energy needs from renewables by 2030.

The most prominent solution in this market segment is solar power and photovoltaics (PV), whose global capacity has been estimated to be approximately 512 gigawatts (GW) by 2018 [1]. Depending on-grid prices, home appliances of PVs systems can be subject to different levels of economic competitiveness [2]. The global PV market is estimated to be 76.6 billion United States Dollars (USD) in 2020 and is projected to grow to 113.1 billion USD by 2025 at a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 8.1% [3]. An adjacent application of solar thermal energy is solar water heating systems, which are considered to be widely adopted and have high technological applicability. The Renewable Energy Policy Network ([REN21](#)) has estimated that about 70 million individual households are utilizing solar water heating systems worldwide [4]. Other surveys have found that it can reduce water heating bills by up to 80% and can potentially have a life cycle of 40 years. Not only that, but concerning their benefits to the environment, these systems have been estimated to reduce approximately 50–70 million metric tons of CO₂ discharge to the atmosphere in the United States of America (USA) alone [5], with 8 billion dollars in retail power costs benefiting the consumers. Solar thermal energy collector systems also include solar thermal space heating applications, which utilize solar energy to heat water or air that is, in turn, circulated in order to heat spaces within buildings. According to an IEA report, in 2021, the solar thermal energy collector area has been estimated to be 1,442,596 m², with the vast majority being in Europe (884,329 m²), followed by Asia excluding China (307,540 m²) [6].

Wind energy is another alternative that has been demonstrated to be efficient and produce electric power while staying environmentally friendly. A prominent example is Denmark, which in 2015 produced 42% of its total electricity demand from the wind. Small or micro wind turbines are another type of green home appliance that can benefit both the household's economy and the environment. Similar to the full-size wind turbines that one may notice scattered across windy places, like mountains or hills, microturbines can be installed at houses, which, when located in designated areas, have been projected to pay the initial cost back within 12 years [7].

Also, according to MarketsAndMarkets reports [8], their market size was 160 million USD in 2017 and 251 million USD in 2022. With this positive type of projections and technological improvements, it is expected that micro wind turbines can be a distributed domestic solution that will supplement large-scale renewable energy production in the next few decades.

Moving on to geothermal energy is another alternative for domestic users, although it can be considered not to be as common as solar and wind. With these types of systems, we can make use of the thermal energy that is transferred from the core of the earth toward the outer layers. Usually, this type of thermal energy is considered slow (0.04-0.06 Watt/m²) and is usually more intense at the boundaries of lithospheric plates. In other words, geothermal energy applications are more efficient at specific locations on earth rather than others, and efficiency is based on hydrogeological conditions. The most notable instances of its practical use are Iceland and Kenya, which produce over 30% of their annual energy needs from geothermal energy sources. Household applications of geothermal systems are less common, though, since deploying systems is highly specific to each case [9] and in most countries, the legislative framework is not mature yet [10]. Although Geothermal Heat Pump Systems have the potential to produce a lot of savings on an individual household level [11], they usually require a considerable amount of area adjacent to the building to that they are applied. This is not very common in modern urban spaces, which leaves household users with the alternative of installing the geothermal heat exchanges vertically into the ground, requiring extra initial setup costs for the digging and installation.

Finally, hydropower is another alternative for renewable energy production, which is one of the oldest and largest technologies. It is based on the concept of extracting energy from the natural flow of water, with the most prominent type of application being hydropower dams which usually use a dam to store river water, which can then be used to flow through turbines that activate a generator that produces electricity. The pumped-storage hydropower technology is not considered to contribute to international markets on the household level significantly, but in contrast, on utility-scale energy storage, it has been reported to account for 95% of Global utility-scale energy storage by the US Department of Energy [12]. Accordingly, hydropower accounts for 37% of the total US renewable energy and 7% of the total US electricity generation [13].

In the context of GBNs, micro-hydro power systems can be utilized if there is running water nearby the designated location. Then the required equipment can be installed (turbines, pump, generator, wiring, etc.), which can usually have at minimum a 10-kilowatt output and provide

enough power for a home, small resort, or small farm. Applications can vary according to the size and type of end-user. Several concerns exist for the future utilization of this technology since its pay-off periods on a small scale are bigger than compared to other renewables [13]. The global small hydropower market (when hydropower plants under 10 MW were accounted for) has been estimated to be 2.5 to 2.7 billion USD in 2019 globally, with North America accounting for 370 to 450 million USD and Europe accounting for 840-950 million USD of that market [14].

3.2 Energy storage

Energy storage at a residential or commercial building level is a trend that technological and scientific advancements have enabled over the past few years. These advancements mainly fall into two categories: battery technologies and thermal energy storage. These types of solutions allow the selective consumption of energy, either from renewable sources when they are available or from saving on energy demand from the electricity grid by exploiting time-of-use tariff policies. This is achieved by controlling and scheduling energy consumption and storing energy, and load balancing. The declining costs of Lithium-Ion batteries are expected to drive the demand for battery energy storage systems for commercial, residential, and utility level storage from 4.4 billion USD in 2022 to 15.1 billion USD in 2027 at a CAGR of 27.9% [15].

Especially in the case of the household energy storage market, where lead-acid batteries are used alongside Lithium-Ion batteries, the demand is expected to rise from 6.26 billion USD in 2019 to 17.54 billion USD in 2024, with a CAGR of 22.28% [16]. Ultimately, with these solutions, a domestic user can store energy from the electricity grid at low demand periods and reduce cost consumption and dependence on the electricity grid during peak hours. Promising results have been delivered in studies [17], where it has been shown that just by load balancing based on energy storage solutions, energy bills can be reduced by at least 20%. It has also been shown that it is possible that in 8 years, these types of systems can "pay back" the CO₂ emissions produced during their manufacturing.

Despite recent advancements in battery technologies and corresponding markets, its initial setup, high costs, and extensive payback periods are leading to this technology not being widely adopted yet. Still, it is adopted in some niche markets by electric vehicle (EV) users [18] or other environmentally concerned users [19]. Overall, with industrial and academic experts discussing the forecasts for this market, it can be distinguished into three types of potential customers interested in this solution: i) users that are looking to use small-scale battery installations to use

time-of-use tariff policies, ii) medium-sized applications, that are usually combined with some renewable source of energy and utilizing the grid as a back source and, iii) finally, larger-scale battery installations, where the homeowner is totally disconnected from the grid. According to published surveys fielded in 2015, in a sample sourced from Queensland, Australia, nearly 70% of respondents are interested in utilizing renewable sources of energy and battery energy storage to disconnect from the existing centralized electricity grid [20].

Thermal energy storage is another solution in the energy storage segment. Regarding thermal energy storage, although its feasibility on a domestic use level has been proven on a research-level [21], it is considered that the technology is not readily accepted in large markets, such as the US [22]. Thermal energy solutions are mainly used on commercial, industrial, and utility levels, with the global market being estimated to be worth about 0.19 billion USD in 2020 and being projected to grow to 0.36 billion USD in 2025 [23]. Despite this relatively small market size, if one considers the environmental benefits projected for thermal energy storage in Europe [24], further R&D in the sector in the next few years can bring more commercialized solutions to the market.

3.3 Heating systems

Heating systems are another segment of the market in green building solutions which can assist to maintain the temperatures of the buildings at the required levels. It is an already established market, with both green and conventional solutions, that is overall defined by the technological trend of becoming more energy efficient. Systems that exist in this market are heat pumps, boilers, furnaces, wood-burning, and pellet stoves, fireplaces, under-the-floor heating, and standalone unit heaters. An overview of the heating solutions segments is given in Figure 2.

Figure 2: GBN solutions within the Heating Solutions Market Segment

The primary type of solution dominating international markets is coal, oil, and natural gas boilers and furnaces. However, in the transition from fossil fuel-based technologies, in 2020, the sales of fossil fuel-based boilers fell below 50% of new equipment, and sales of heat pumps and renewable heating equipment (solar hot water systems) reached more than 20% of overall installations [25]. With fossil fuel-based boiler and furnaces reducing their emissions and their well-established reputation (manufacturers provide guarantees of up to several decades), they are still considered heavy polluters of the environment, and their market share is required to fall to zero so that zero-emissions targets, as set by green initiatives worldwide, are reached. In that respect, it is expected that governments and policymakers will introduce incentives to phase out the sales of such equipment.

On the other hand, according to a report [26] by the International Energy Association (IEA), almost 180 million heat pumps were used for heating in 2020, increasing by 10% over the last five years. They are considered the fastest-growing market in the heating space. While it is a technology that is usually incorporated into new buildings, it only accounts for 7% of global heating demand. The heat pumps EU market is considered to be expanding quickly, with approximately 1.8 million domestic users installing heat pumps in their houses (leading to a 12% annual average growth since 2015). An often-discussed barrier to their adoption is their seasonal performance factor, which, as technology progresses and performance is improved, has become an issue of lesser importance. However, the flexibility (ductless, ability to provide heating to one room and at the same time cooling to another) that some of these systems present, such as Variable Refrigerant Flow (VRF) Heat Pumps, has led to significant commercial exploitation of such systems, with VRF heat pumps market growing from 17.55 billion USD in 2020 to 31.9 billion USD in 2025.

Modern hearth appliances are another type of solution available that includes hearth appliances with a contemporary design based on different fuels such as electricity, wood, gas, and pellet. The market was estimated at 7.7 billion USD in 2020 and is projected to reach 9.7 billion USD in 2025 with a CAGR of 4.7% [27]. These types of systems can be distinguished into modern hearths (vented), which usually include some fan or pump to distribute heat, and traditional ones (unvented), which have been used since ancient times. Based on fuel consumed corresponds to different market sizes: Wood-burning appliances accounted for 0.66 billion USD in 2020, and 0.45 billion USD in 2020 for pellet-burning hearths. The wood-burning appliances market is expected to contract to 0.54 billion in 2025, and the pellet-burning appliances market is expected to grow to 0.59 billion USD in 2025. Accordingly, electricity-powered hearths are

expected to grow from 4.16 billion USD in 2020 to 5.43 billion USD in 2025. Gas-powered hearths are also a type of solution within the market that is expected to grow from 2.41 billion USD in 2020 to 3.1 billion USD in 2025 [27]. In Figure 3, a pie chart of hearth market segmentation by fuel type is provided.

Figure 3: Hearth market size by fuel type in 2021 [adapted from [27]]

A pellet stoves market is further analysed next. With wood burning being prohibited in some places due to high emissions and air pollution that is caused by it—moving on to heating solutions based on wood pellet stoves and furnaces, which utilize pellet, a renewable source, as a biofuel for mainly electricity generation or for heat production. The global wood pellet market has increased on average by 14% each year since 2011, with the EU accounting for 54% of global production in 2015 and North America accounting for 35% [28]. The EU consumes 75% of global pellet production, with 64% being accounted for heat generation, of which 42% is consumed by residential users. Applications range from single individual stoves to central heating boilers, with the medium-scale pellet sector, which includes applications greater than 50 kilowatts (kW), being one of the most promising markets in Europe (market growth of 16% in 2015) [29], it is expected that pellet can be an excellent alternative to conventional heating solutions.

Another solution that mainly concerns installations in new buildings is the under-the-floor heating group of solutions, which is considered to be a green alternative for heating in residential use. It is believed that this solution is not widely adopted and that advancements in related technology would be required in order to reduce the upfront cost that is needed for household owners in order to install such a system. Growing demand for cost-effective heating systems is expected to drive their market growth from 4.8 billion USD in 2022 to approximately 7 billion USD in 2027 [30]. On the contrary, a solution that requires minimal upfront investment and is widely adopted is space heaters. The most common appliances are small electric resistance space heaters that require no installation and can be directly plugged into a wall outlet. Their heating capacity usually ranges between 10,000 and 45,000 BTU (British thermal

unit) per hour, and the main concern for them is safety. These are considered to have a supplementary role in home heating, but they are also used as a primary source of heating when using another type of heating system is not an option. Another option is static and dynamic heat accumulators, which accumulate energy during low-energy demand periods, store it, and provide it in the form of heat for the building throughout the day. The difference between static and dynamic heat accumulators is that the latter includes a fan that controls the energy/heat discharge throughout the day.

3.4 Ventilation systems

Ventilation systems are usually mechanical systems that can be used to mainly handle airflow within the building in order to: *i)* Promote health and well-being by reducing pollutants that enter or leave the building, *ii)* Ensure thermal comfort by cooperating with other heating and cooling systems, *iii)* Measure the environmental impact of building internal function (especially for commercial and industrial use).

Ventilation systems can be further classified into Air-Handling Units (AHUs), air filters, dehumidifiers, ventilation fans, humidifiers, and air purifiers. Based on recent reports [31], the ventilation equipment market has been estimated to be 24.21 billion USD globally in 2021 and is projected to grow to 30.12 billion USD in 2026 at a CAGR of 5.7%. Overall, the residential ventilation market was estimated to be 4.7 billion USD in 2021, while the commercial and industrial sectors were estimated to be worth 10.8 and 8.7 billion USD each. Regarding future projections, the ventilations systems residential market is expected to grow to 6 billion USD, with the commercial and industrial sectors being expected to grow at a faster rate to 14.5 billion USD and 11.4 billion USD.

Regarding the first type of system, AHUs are usually installed for very large spaces that accumulate a lot of people at the same time (e.g., hotel dining rooms, convention halls, restaurants). They include purification filters, an air conditioning system (including both heating and cooling coils), and humidity monitoring and management to provide the necessary airflow that guarantees comfort and hygiene within the building. So, in essence, they combine temperature control functionality and are an all-in-one solution that is suitable for the specific type of needs when other standalone solutions cannot be installed or as efficient. They are also used for commercial and residential use and can be installed on the building roof, basement, or on some of the floors. There can also be multiple AHUs at buildings according to the building's

zones and special needs. Overall, AHUs accounted for 10.6 billion USD and are expected to grow to 14.23 billion USD in 2026.

Another type of ventilation solution is the generic air filters. They can be installed within AHUs or as a standalone solution that only controls air quality and cleans the air by removing pollutants. The air filters can be in-flow filters or outflow filters, with in-flow filters cleaning the air that comes from outside the building to the inside, and the outflow filters cleaning the air that is channelled towards the environment. The first is more usual for household use, and especially when residents are prone to health risks, while the second is more suitable for commercial and industrial use, where pollutants created by some process need to be collected from outflow air and disposed of under specific conditions (e.g., buried into the ground). The generic air filters market accounted for 6.39 billion USD in 2021 and is estimated to grow to 8.72 billion in 2026 at a CAGR of 4.7%.

A few other types of solutions exist within the ventilation systems market that is estimated to be smaller segments of the overall market. One of them is ventilation fans which are estimated to be 2.05 billion USD in 2021, and a relatively small growth is expected at 2.64 billion USD in 2026. Another smaller segment is air purifiers which not only filter the air but also sanitize it and do not only remove particles as filters do. The air purifiers market is estimated to be 0.69 billion USD in 2021 and is expected to grow to 1.32 billion USD in 2026. In Figure 4 below, one can notice the overall market share for each type of ventilation solution.

Figure 4: Ventilation equipment market percentage projection by 2026

3.5 Cooling systems

This market segment is comprised of solutions that can help users and buildings to keep certain spaces below a certain temperature. The end-user may need such a type of solution if they are located in warmer climates, so they may potentially need to reduce the temperature of the building that they reside or because the space building that they use need to be refrigerated due

to designated needs (e.g., cold storage facilities, refrigerated warehouses, etc.). Mainly four types of solutions can be identified in this market, the first being Air-Conditioning (AC) technologies, which are the dominant solution in the market, and then there are household fan solutions and dehumidification systems, and evaporative coolers.

AC systems worldwide annual sales have almost quadrupled from 1990 to 2016, with domestic users accounting for 1093 million installed units and 94 million annual sales in 2016. In terms of GW output capacity, residential users' already installed systems account for 6181 GW, with 848 GW new capacity established in 2016 [32]. AC sales differ between different regions of the world, with 40% of all cooling capacity and 50% of residential sector capacity being installed in the US. According to the same report by IEA, the overwhelming capacity of deployed AC systems is split-type air conditioners that require an indoor and outdoor unit, often connected with copper tubing. Split systems, in comparison with other larger applications of ACs (central AC systems), are installed relatively simply, unobtrusively, with no need for extensive ductwork. Evaporative coolers are AC systems with a smaller market segment. Based on the water phase transition principle, evaporative coolers are considered more energy-efficient and environmentally friendly than established AC technology by requiring approximately one-fourth of the energy that an AC cooler would require. Their maintenance needs, reliance on a water source, and the extra humidity that they add to the air of a house are considered their main drawbacks.

Moving on to household electric fans is another widespread form of cooling, with 55% of all households globally owning at least one fan [32]. They have several advantages over other forms of cooling since they are cheap to buy, come in a wide range of sizes, and can be portable. It is estimated that they need approximately 10% of the energy that AC would require and are very important in developing countries. Electric fans are especially well-adopted across regions with developing economies and warm climates, where air conditioning technologies are too expensive to acquire.

Finally, dehumidification systems are another option in the cooling market segment, where this system is used to control humidity inside a building. They are especially advantageous when a user needs to lower the humidity content of the air inside the house, which, especially in warm and humid climates, leads to a lowering of the temperature of the building. Dehumidification systems are used in a wide array of use cases such on both the household level and commercial levels (indoor ice rinks, pools, storage warehouses, etc.) and are also cooperatively used along a ventilation system/functionality (e.g., filtering, fans air purifiers). The overall dehumidifiers

market has been estimated to be 2.93 billion USD in 2021 and is expected to grow to 3.87 billion in 2026 at a CAGR of 5.7%.

3.6 Building envelope solutions

Under this market, we include a series of solutions that are installed in buildings with the aim of reducing the building's heating and cooling needs, the overall energy consumption as well as reducing the environmental impact of its operations. The solutions are passive because they are usually integrated into the building, last for several years, and do not need to be activated in order to provide their benefits. Several principles are attempted to be held to achieve the aforementioned aims, such as using green recycled/upcycled insulation materials to achieve thermal and moisture control, noise reduction, as well as airtightness, which enables controlling air transfer from the environment to the inside of the house, and vice versa.

Several parts of a building can be insulated based on a green solution to achieve better energy efficiency. Green insulation material is, in essence, a material that can be used to protect a building but has several green properties meaning that it is recycled, upcycled, non-toxic, or organic. Regarding the market of green insulation material, wall insulation solutions are estimated [33] to be most used in approximately 47% of the EU market. Next, roof insulation application is preferred at 37% and floor insulation at 15%. According to the same report [33], the global market of green building solutions is estimated at 22.73 billion USD in 2015 and is expected to reach 38.69 billion USD by 2027.

Apart from green insulation materials, conventional insulation materials can benefit homeowners and reduce energy consumption and energy efficiency. Materials such as fiberglass and mineral wool, polystyrene, and polyisocyanurate are considered as such. Their application for domestic insulation is proven, and although they are not "fully green", they can still derive benefits for both the environment and their users, such as in the study by Levy et al. [34], where the authors demonstrate that increased residential insulation (i.e., conventional) for a single year's cohort of new homes can lead to reductions of 180 GWh of electricity consumption per year, which in turn can lead to about 470,000 fewer tons of CO₂ emissions per year. Regarding the related market size, the building thermal insulation market size was estimated at 12,039.3 kilotons of material for 2022, and the demand is attributed to materials such as plastic foam and glass wool. Emerging economies such as India and China offer profitable growth opportunities, especially in the roofing market, which has been estimated [35] to rise from 168 billion USD in 2016 to 213.45 billion USD in 2021 and is further projected to grow to 270.4 billion in 2026 [35].

In Figure 5 below, a pie chart of the estimated insulation market segments' sizes per geographical location is provided for 2022.

Figure 5: Insulation market segments size per region in 2022 [adapted from [36]]

3.7 Construction and lifecycle assessment and improvement

Buildings and their several components are subject to specific lifecycles not just from an operational side but throughout the phases of design, construction, operation, demolition, and waste treatment. One of the emerging topics in modern research is the lifecycle analysis (LCA) and lifecycle costing (LCC) of building materials and components [37], with the ultimate goal of assessing the energy and raw resources that they would require, as well as the overall environmental impact of their use.

The importance of lifecycle analysis tools is becoming more and more important in the construction sector, where these can be utilized for budgeting as well as to assess design alternatives for new projects. Although it is based on the principles of engineering economy [38], its origins are hard to trace, and it is believed to be first used by the U.S. Department of Defence in the mid-1960s in order to assist in the procurement of military equipment [39][40]. There are several types of variables to consider in such analysis, which can lead to different accuracy of results and better management of the building during that lifecycle. In the last few decades, there has been a development of Building Information Modelling (BIM), Digital Twin (DT) models, robot agents, and sensing devices, which can help engineers and practitioners in the field of construction to better understand and design buildings and their blueprints.

One type of solution that can support construction and lifecycle assessment is BIM-based lifecycle planning has been used for individual buildings and the sustainable planning of cities in which planners have been able to reduce maintenance costs and overall resource consumption [41]. According to the report with the title "Building Information Modelling Market – Forecast

to 2026," which was published in October 2021 [42], the market was valued at 5.4 billion USD in 2020 and is projected to reach 10.7 billion USD by 2026 with a CAGR of 12.5%. This upward trend in the BIM can be attributed to several factors, such as the rising trend of Internet of Things (IoT)-aided applications in the construction sector [43], the low level of digitalization in the construction industry over the last few decades as well as the increased urbanization across the world. Finally, a concern that may hinder the adoption process of BIM solutions for lifecycle assessment and analysis is the initial investment cost required to acquire such solutions [44].

The digitalization of the building planning and construction phase is further enhanced by the utilization of a wireless sensor network that can be deployed in the construction phase to monitor the building and the construction process. One of the main use cases is that sensor networks, when optimally deployed, can collect and upload data to a cloud service that can then be used for real-time visualization, climate control, or further analysis through machine learning and analytics [45]. Several stages of a construction lifecycle can be optimized in this way, the calculation of construction performance indicators (based on sensor network data) enabling improved decision-making as compared to empirical performance assessment performed by construction workers or managers [46].

According to recent reports [47], due to the increasing demand for predictive maintenance and business optimizations, the (Digital Twins) DTs' market size across all industries is expected to grow from 3.2 billion USD in 2020 to 48.27 billion USD in 2026, with a CAGR of 58%. In the case of Residential buildings' DT, the growth is estimated to rise from 187 million USD to 1.41 billion in 2025. DT applications can be deployed for a single house or apartment or a multi-story complex and can be integrated with the Building Information Model (BIM) for the physical and structural properties of a building. This type of information can provide benefits for both the construction phase of a building, reducing costs, timelines, and environmental impact, and offer benefits to the operation of the building after its construction, during its entire lifecycle, from construction to demolition. Specifically, regarding the construction phase, DTs can employ several models for the different digital or physical systems within the building and serve as a very detailed model or blueprint for successful design and construction.

Another concept that is still in its infancy is the robot systems that can help make building construction more efficient. These types of robot systems are expected to work collaboratively with human construction workers and help them accelerate project delivery phases as well as reduce overall costs. Several types of robot systems are considered in the scientific literature, from Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) to Unmanned Ground Vehicles (UGVs). Other types of

robotic equipment that can be used are robotic arms and exoskeleton devices that can be used as implants for construction workers. However, this type of innovative solution is mostly in the R&D phases, with the respective market growing (at a CAGR of 16.8%) from 76.7 million in 2018 to 166.4 million in 2023 (est.) [48].

3.8 Smart Energy Management solutions

Another segment of the GBNs solutions market is the Smart Energy Management solutions market, which contains software and hardware platforms, Digital Twins (DT, DTs), digital models, decision support tools, Internet Communication Technologies (ICT), and sensor networks to measure, monitor, simulate and help manage the building's energy consumption during the operation of the building. To achieve these goals, intelligent energy management solutions incorporate a series of smart products and services based on analytics, smart devices, sensors, and networking capabilities to help control lights, heating, cooling, and consumption from the grid in between high and low-demand periods within a day. They also enable measuring, monitoring, and simulating the different aspects of a building's energy operations. Still, these features are usually running as background processes, with only several control features being provided to the end-user. They can further help users to understand their power consumption habits and hopefully improve them. In a report from 2014 [49], it has been reported that smart energy management solutions have a potential of more than 30% in consumption savings for their users, while in other reports [50], a significant potential for adoption is presented. However, several barriers have been discussed [51] regarding their adoption, such as interoperability and security of service, and the extra energy consumption that they may bring.

Generally, smart energy management can be further achieved by Digital Twin models that focus on the operational phase of the building. As described in Section 3.7 above, the DT market is growing globally with applications across several use cases and for different end-users (residential, commercial, public, and infrastructure buildings). The importance of DT models during the operational phase of the building grows along with the size of the building to be managed. For example, DTs can be especially useful in vast buildings or infrastructures, like sports stadiums or railway network facilities, where managing the multiple buildings within such building systems can be hard if this management only relies on the human factor. Similarly, in residential buildings, DTs can help reduce energy consumption and effort towards management, especially in multi-story buildings [52]. In Table 2 below, one can notice the anticipated market sizes for DT applications for several types of buildings.

Type	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2023	2025
Commercial Buildings	161	207	272	360	514	744	1,642	3,736
Residential Buildings	56	73	97	130	187	273	612	1,417
Public Buildings	68	88	116	155	223	325	727	1,675
Infrastructure	296	375	485	635	894	1,275	2,738	6,055
Total	582	744	970	1,280	1,818	2,617	5,719	12,883

Table 2: Market sizes for Digital Twin applications by the different types of buildings (source: [53])

Smart energy management systems have also enabled the concept of positive energy buildings or active buildings, which, as agents of the wider smart grid system of a GBN, can contribute energy back to the grid. For this, there needs to be energy production (through renewables), and energy storage, and then exchange this excess energy with the grid through local smart management and net metering options. These capabilities for GBNs are uniquely useful when one considers that inside an active distribution network, we can have buildings that facilitate different needs: *i)* office spaces, *ii)* households, *iii)* charging EVs that cover travel demand, *iv)* keeping temperatures steady for spaces and HVAC appliances throughout the day [54]. For these reasons, active building systems are gaining more and more attention in the last few years, both in research [55] and marketwise [56]. Solutions that enable positive energy buildings are connected to the wider Smart Grid Market, which is expected to grow from 43.1 billion USD in 2021 to 103.4 billion USD in 2026, with a CAGR of 19.1%.

Finally, although some would consider them part of the wider Digital Twin or smart energy management platform, several stand-alone smart appliances exist that can provide small-scale benefits to households and at a limited cost when they are acquired separately. This type of device usually includes a minor part of the functionality of a DT and is based on appliances such as sensors, thermostats, fans, and lighting modules that can be smartly controlled (possibly through a smartphone application) according to environment variables and user preferences, usually leading toward less energy consumption and a more comfortable living environment. They can be mass-produced and typically have low cost, with the increasing number of internet users, urbanization, and increasing disposable income in developing countries leading to growth in the market over forecasted periods, with reports estimating that the market value will rise from 84.5 billion USD in 2021 to 138.9 billion USD in 2026 [57].

3.9 The social dimension of Green Building Neighbourhoods market segmentation: Technologies and Innovations for Inclusive and Sustainable Communities

The GBN concept, as defined in PROBONO, is at the forefront of creating sustainable and eco-friendly European communities. While environmental considerations are vital, it is equally important to address the social dimension within the GBNs of the future. This deliverable explores the significance of incorporating social aspects into GBNs and highlights technologies and innovations that promote community well-being, inclusivity, and high quality of life. Creating sustainable communities goes beyond energy efficiency and resource conservation it has been traditionally considered. The social dimension considers community engagement, social equity, health, and well-being. By integrating these elements, GBNs can foster a sense of belonging, improve residents' quality of life, and create a thriving and inclusive environment.

In that sense, several PROBONO outcomes may be social outcomes or innovations that may support the deployment of GBNs but are not necessarily market-oriented products or services. Thus, this market segmentation is extended to outline expected groups of social outcomes that can support the social integration and engagement of people in GBNs and the wider GBN concept. To begin with, technologies such as community platforms, mobile apps, and online portals provide avenues for active community engagement. These platforms facilitate communication, collaboration, and participation in decision-making, giving residents a voice in shaping their neighbourhoods. Furthermore, virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) technologies can enhance community engagement by allowing residents to visualize and provide feedback on proposed designs or urban planning initiatives. Smart technologies and innovations play a significant role in promoting accessibility within GBNs. For instance, smart home systems with voice commands and automation can assist individuals with mobility challenges. Universal design principles integrated into building planning and infrastructure can create barrier-free environments, ensuring that everyone, regardless of age or ability, can easily access amenities and services within the neighbourhood. BIM models can play an important role in this discussion since these can serve as one of the 'building-blocks' towards the digital integration of modern technologies and traditional research that has been being developed in the scientific literature [58].

Another important group of social innovation artefacts that can be expected are the health-focused innovations that may trigger the interest of communities in the GBN concept. With air pollution in Europe being one of the main concerns of the EC [59], technologies promoting health and well-being in GBNs are gaining momentum. Sensor-based systems can monitor air

quality, temperature, and humidity, ensuring optimal indoor environments. Integrating green spaces, urban gardens, and biophilic design elements within neighbourhoods contribute to mental and physical well-being. Smart fitness devices, wellness apps, and community health programs can encourage active lifestyles and foster a strong sense of community.

As PROBONO is an R&D project, it is important to include all the research and educational assets that may further increase the awareness and competency of professionals in European communities. Online learning platforms, interactive apps, and virtual simulations can educate residents about sustainable practices, energy conservation, waste management, and the importance of biodiversity. Community-driven initiatives, such as workshops, webinars, and skill-sharing platforms, provide opportunities for residents to learn from experts and exchange knowledge, fostering a culture of sustainability within the neighbourhood. With that being said, we include Figure 6 below, where the eight market segments of PROBONO are included, as well as the social dimension which connects and is expected to affect GBN markets.

Figure 6: Market segments for GBNs solutions including the social dimension artefacts

3.10 Market Segmentation Conclusion

Facilitating the development of GBNs is definitely one of the biggest challenges of the next decades, especially when one considers the current pace of urbanization in Europe. Based on Eurostat data from 2016 [60], the number of people living in rural areas of the EU-28 is expected to fall by 7.9 million in 2050 to account for 20% of the E.U. population, with these people moving

to cities, towns, and suburbs. Based on the same data source, E.U.'s urban population continues to rise and has almost accounted for three-quarters (72.5%) of the EU-28 inhabitants in 2014.

With such increases, the importance of GBNs as the cells of the sustainable European cities of the future will only grow in the foreseeable future. In the attempt to provide the building blocks for the GBNs, several solutions currently exist in markets, as described in the current report. Hopefully, with the proper political coordination on an EU level and initiatives from MS, current and future innovative solutions can be adopted in practice and help reduce energy consumption and the environmental impact and improve the quality of life in European urban environments.

In Figure 7 below, an overview of the solutions is given.

Renewable energy generation solutions	Energy storage solutions	Heating systems	Ventilation systems	Cooling systems	Building envelope solutions	Construction and lifecycle assessment and improvement	Smart Energy Management
Solar PV Panels	Battery applications	Fossil fuel furnaces	Air handling units	Split-type AC systems	Green insulation materials	Lifecycle assessment and analysis tools	ICT monitoring platforms
Solar Water Heaters	Thermal energy storage	Heat pumps	Air filters	Central AC systems	Conventional insulation materials	Digital Twin platforms (design phase)	Smart energy management platforms
Wind energy and micro-turbines		Hearths	Ventilation fans	Electric fan systems		BIM-based lifecycle assessment	Digital Twin platforms (operational phase)
Geothermal energy solutions		Pellet stoves	Air purifiers	Dehumidification systems		Application of robotics	Active building & Net metering solutions
Micro-hydropower solutions		Underfloor heating		Evaporative coolers		Wireless sensor networks	Smaller-scale smart appliances
		Electric resistance heaters					
		Heat accumulators					

Figure 7: Market segmentation overview alongside the groups of solutions per segment

With all the information in the current market segmentation, PROBONO partners can utilize the analysis within deliverable D9.1 and Task 9.1.2 to better understand the GBN market and position their products and services. In this way, with follow-up analysis of customer target segments based on the already included segment sizes and solutions included. Customer analysis and behaviour analysis can occur, accompanied by targeted marketing campaigns, that will likely result in higher ROIs than non-targeted campaigns. Finally, this segmentation may also support product and service owners within PROBONO partner organizations to understand competition and competitive solutions within segments that would previously not be considered. Overall, since this market segmentation is expected to cover all of the marketable outcomes of PROBONO, PROBONO partners have the opportunity to have a high-level view of solutions and technology trends in other adjacent fields other than their own, having a more spherical opinion of trends within the GBN domain.

4 Market Indicators for GBN Solutions

This chapter is related to the subtask ST9.1.1 (Market Indicators). Based on the market segments identified in chapter 3 within ST9.1.2, qualitative and quantitative market indicators have been gathered and grouped for each of the segments. The indicators are then clustered into three main impacts categories: techno-economic, environmental, and social indicators. The three aspects enable an overview into the market in terms of commercial potential, buying patterns, social acceptance, and environmental aspects of the technology in a comparative way. The indicators also serve as a basis to facilitate and understand the market potential of the solutions selected for implementation in the PROBONO living labs, as well as the potential for future exploitation beyond the project. The market indicators are gathered and identified from literature and market research (in section 4.1) and then validated through interviews (in section 4.2) with the technology partners and living labs responsible within the consortium. This step ensures the alignment and relevance of the market analysis for the work within WP9 for replicability, exploitation, and commercialisation.

In section 4.2 of this deliverable, the grouped indicators per segment are gathered in a compact, and easy-to-read format, bar charts, radar charts, and tables. They are validated with the project partners within the PROBONO project who are working towards the implementation of GBN solutions either as a technical partner or a Living Lab coordinator. The validation takes part through one-to-one interviews aiming to analyse their role within the implementation, how they relate to the gathered indicators, and finally suggestions on how to refine the indicators that cater to and better represent PROBONO's implemented solutions in the future. After the feedback is collected and analysed, it was used to improve on the previous section within this deliverable. This would also serve to highlight the importance of each category (environmental, techno-economic, or social) and its relevance in decision making within PROBONO technology/solutions providers and living labs.

4.1 Market indicators based on categories

This section gathers and analyses the market indicators based on the technologies for each segment described in chapter 3, with an exception to this method is the last segments: Construction and LCA in design phase and smart energy management solutions in use phase. The utilisation of these systems is often considered as a supporting mechanism for the implementation. During the design phase of a construction or renovation project, Building Information Modelling (BIM), and Building Energy Modelling (BEM) could be integrated with an

environmental impact assessment tool to act as a decision support system for the designer. While the smart energy management of assets during the use phase are related to optimisation of the technologies installed achieving energy savings and prolonging the lifetime of the system. Now, we see a detailed analysis of the market indicators in the sections below.

4.1.1 Environmental indicators

Typically, a Green Building aims to improve on the environmental performance compared to business-as-usual. To assess that change, sets of environmental indicators are gathered from the market and literature available for each PROBONO segment. Priority has been given to Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) results covering all the life cycle stages of a solution (i.e., Manufacturing, Installation and usage, and End of life) as it provides a holistic overview of the impacts. When not available, a comparative study including only parts of the life cycle was considered instead. The goal is to present a comparative view of the various solutions in each segment.

It should be noted that the context, data quality and assumptions are very important when examining any LCA results. Comparability is therefore not recommended when considering different study conditions and it will be noted to present findings from different sources independently. The approach taken will be to nominate the best suitable set of comparative indicators to present while considering results from different sources in a qualitative way to support the results and conclusions.

1. Renewable energy generation solutions

Several studies considered all or some of the PROBONO solutions identified in this segment, however, the context is usually different from small scale and distributed generation. A review report [61] published by the American National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) presents the harmonized results of around 3000 LCA studies on utility-scale generation. This report presents the harmonized lifecycle greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions for generating 1 MWh of electric energy from six types of power plants including both renewable and non-renewable sources. The results indicate that the average GHG emissions for PV, concentrated solar thermal power (CSP) and wind are 45, 30, and 10.5 kg CO₂-eq respectively. While the average emissions from natural gas and coal plants are 475 and 1000 respectively.

It can be observed that the worst performing renewable energy in terms of lifecycle carbon footprint is still emitting less than 10% of natural gas plants without carbon capture and sequestration. To consider other environmental impacts beyond GHG emissions, a report by Eionet [62] titled "A life cycle perspective on the benefits of renewable electricity generation"

was taken into consideration. It reports on the environmental impacts of various renewable energy sources taking the Cradle to Gate approach which considers only the manufacturing and generation of electricity up to the point of delivery to the grid without considering the usage stage or the end-of-life stages.

The considered indicators include Global warming potential¹⁰ (GWP), Eutrophication Potential (EP), Acidification Potential (AP), Particulate Matter emissions (PM), freshwater Ecotoxicity (Ecot) and Land occupation (Lnd). The results are summarized in Figure 8 showing the ranking of each technology in terms of the various impact indicators with 1 being the least impacting and 5 being the most impacting. It can be observed from the plot that Hydro power is the better performer in all indicators except for land occupation due to the civil work required for any large-scale plants. The second-best performer is still Wind power which shows low impact in almost all indicators considered. Photovoltaic plants are performing the worst according to the study due to the embodied emissions in the components and materials used, despite the virtually zero emissions during its operation.

Figure 8: Ranking the environmental indicators of renewable energy solutions considered for PROBONO, adapted from [62].

Other studies done by the World Nuclear Association [63] and B. Peupartier [64] show the same trends in environmental indicators comparing the renewable energy solutions in different other

¹⁰ The GWP indicator is used interchangeably with GHG emissions here since both are aggregated into their CO₂-equivalent according to IPCC characterization factors.

scenarios and geographical settings. This strengthens the credibility of the impact indicators gathered.

2. Energy storage

a. Batteries

Considering first the electric storage in Batteries, a comparative LCA study [65] looks into the manufacturing, usage, and disposal of Lead-acid batteries compared to 3 types of Lithium-ion batteries available in the market. The relevant indicators assessed in that article include Global warming potential (GWP), Acidification potential, Resource use-fossil (ADP-fossil), resource use-mineral and metals (ADP-metal) and Particulate matter (PM). The resulting indicators considering 1 kWh of stored energy during the lifetime of each type of battery put forward lithium-ion batteries as a greener option compared to lead-acid batteries as their manufacturing is less harmful to the environment. A summary of the results can be found in Table 3, showing that NCA-type Li-ion batteries have the lowest lifecycle GHG emissions and resources depletion impacts which are often considered the biggest challenge in battery manufacturing as metals and minerals become more rare.

Indicators	Lead Acid	Lithium-ion		
		LFP	NMC	NCA
GWP [kgCO ₂ -eq/kWh]	2	1.64	1.22	1.1
Acidification potential [mol H ⁺ eq./kWh]	0.02	0.0202	0.0066	0.0124
Resource use, fossil [MJ/kWh]	33	25.08	20.46	18.15
Resource use, metals [kg/kWh]	8.00E-04	4.80E-05	8.80E-05	5.60E-05
Particulate matter [disease incidence]	1.00E-07	1.35E-07	4.80E-08	4.80E-08

Table 3: Environmental impacts of Lead-acid vs Li-ion batteries, adapted from [65]

Another study conducted in 2012 [66] investigated the LCA environmental of Lead-acid, Li-ion, and three other types of batteries based on older data sources. While comparing the results of two different LCA studies is very complicated, one small conclusion could be safely drawn from this study and that is Lithium ion battery technology has improved both technologically and environmentally in recent years and is projected to improve more as the market grows.

Another type of batteries that has been growing in the market lately as a replacement to lead-acid and lithium-ion is flow batteries. The article [67] tackles the comparison between lithium ion batteries and flow batteries from a different approach. The authors are comparing the two storage technologies while coupled with wind and/or PV generation in grid applications. The results are summarized in Table 4 as values for each MWh of electric energy stored during the

lifetime of the battery. The indicators are similar to the ones described previously with the addition of the cumulative energy demand. The two types of batteries are close competitors on the environmental side: flow batteries are less impactful in 4 out of 5 indicators except for the energy energy and fossil use that are in favor of lithium ion batteries. It is often considered that the technological advancement and scale effect in manufacturing of lithium ion is giving it the edge in competition.

Indicators	Lithium Ion		Vanadium Redox Flow (VRF)	
	with PV	with Wind	with PV	with Wind
GWP [kg CO2 eq.]	95	72.2	100.8	72.4
PM [kg PM2.5 eq]	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.3
AP [kg SO2 eq]	1.2	1.1	0.8	0.7
Human Toxicity [kg 1,4-DCB]	218.2	199.4	173.8	150.5
Resource use, metals [kg Fe-eq]	5.9	5.5	5.9	5.4
Resource use, fossils [kg oil-eq]	23	17.3	25.5	18.4
Cumulative energy demand [MJ]	2734.1	2389.5	3129.5	2702.3

Table 4: Environmental impact indicators of Li-ion vs VRF batteries coupled with PV and Wind energy [67]

A recent white paper [68] published by CellCube, a USA-based flow batteries manufacturer, summarises the outcome from a LCA and sensitivity analysis for their vanadium-redox flow battery (VRFB) and a lithium-ion battery (LiB) under the assumptions: 20 years lifetime, powered by the same renewable energy, and taking a reference unit of one MWh of capacity. As shown in Table 5, in the case of using all virgin materials, flow batteries show reduced carbon footprint compared to LiB. Furthermore, the paper stresses the superior recyclability of flow batteries which would cause the carbon footprint from the manufacturing phase be 66% lower compared to not using any recycled materials in the manufacturing.

Carbon footprint (in kgCO ₂ -eq per MWh)	Weber VRFB	Weber LiB	Enerox VRFB
Manufactured from virgin materials	38.2	58	32.6
Considering recycled and reused materials	10	42	11.1

Table 5: Comparison of the carbon footprint of flow batteries and lithium-ion batteries, adapted from [68]

b. Thermal energy storage

The life cycle assessment of thermal energy storage (TES) for buildings has been studied in various articles with different technologies. According to the review paper by I. Hayatina et al. [69], the addition of sensible heat energy storage systems like a Water tank leads to overall lifetime improvement in energy consumption as well as reductions in environmental impacts, while the usage of latent heat TES like Phase-change materials (PCM) or ice can reduce environmental impacts too but typically performs worse compared to sensible heat TES. The

main advantage of latent heat technologies is that it takes less volume compared to prominent solutions like hot water tanks. The authors also indicate that climatic dependencies may arise with the use of certain PCM thermal storage.

S. Thaker, et al. [70] analyse five specific configurations of TES used in concentrated solar thermal power plants with one latent heat storage, one thermochemical storage technology and three configurations of sensible heat tanks (from which only the simplest one is included here). The resulting environmental indicators are in terms of GHG emissions in gCO₂ per kWh thermal energy stored and Net energy ratio which is defined as thermal energy stored during the life time of the technology divided by the fossil fuel energy used during the lifecycle up to dismantling and disposal. As shown from the results in Table 6, the sensible heat tank performs the best both in least amount of GHG emissions and highest energy ratio with the main disadvantage being the high volume requirement.

Indicator	Direct STES tank	LTES tank	Chemical TES
GHG [gCO ₂ /kWh]	11	20	18
Net energy ratio	25	2	7.5

Table 6: Environmental impact indicators of three typologies of thermal energy storage, adapted from [70]

The same conclusions was reinforced by other earlier studies with the same CSP context and specific types of TES used. One of which is the article by E. Oró et al. [71]. The authors considered a multi-indicator criteria with Eco system quality, human health and resource use indicators. The sensible heat options were less impactful in all categories compared to latent heat storage such as PCM.

3. HVAC systems

The energy systems used for heating and cooling are often put in the same category as heat transfer devices. One notable 2008 study by V.P. Shah et al. [72] takes into consideration three different configurations for heating in winter and cooling in summer, namely a furnace+AC, Boiler+AC and a Heat pump for both functions. The systems were simulated over 35 years and a LCA was conducted to consider the manufacturing, installation, maintenance and energy consumption of the different systems in 4 different states with different climatic conditions, and energy mixes. Considering first the impacts from the manufacturing and infrastructure of the three systems, it is safe to assume that having only one system for both heating and cooling is less impactful in all categories as shown in Table 7.

Normalized indicator	Furnace + AC	Boiler + AC	Heat pump
Climate change	0.27	0.43	0.22

Ecosystem quality	0.06	0.07	0.05
Resource use	0.32	0.38	0.3
Human health	0.52	1.09	0.43

Table 7: Normalized environmental indicators for manufacturing of three heating and cooling systems used in buildings, adapted from [72]

However, when considering the energy consumption during the lifetime of the equipment, the results indicate that when the energy mix is greener (the case of Oregon with 67% hydro power), the heat pump system has the lowest impact in all categories. On the contrary, in the state of Texas where +80% of the electricity comes from coal and natural gas plants, the heat pump has the highest scores in all impact categories due to the high usage of cooling during the hot summer. The author supplements this claim by a sensitivity analysis to measure at which electricity generation mix the heat pump system would have the lowest impact in each of the other systems.

A more recent study by H. Lin et al. [73] suggests similar results for heating systems considering a Gas boiler only system, and a hybrid gas boiler + Heat pump system simulated in a building in the UK. The resulting environmental indicators summarized in Table 8 show the impacts associated with delivering space heating for the duration of 20 years. One could see the dependency of the heat pump system on the electricity mix as for most indicators the impact is less with a more renewable mix represented by the 2050 mix. Furthermore, some of the impacts are lower when using only the boiler as the manufacturing of two systems has higher impact compared to the boiler only.

Indicators	Gas boiler only	Hybrid system (HP + Boiler)	
		2018 Mix	2050 Mix
GWP [kg CO2-eq]	6.4	4.5	3.5
Ozone Depletion [kg CFC-eq]	3.6	3.7	4.8
Acidification Potential [kg SO2-eq]	1.5	1.1	0.8
Human toxicity [kg 1,4-DB-eq]	0.6	1.8	1.8
Photochemical oxidation [kg NMVOC]	7.6	6.2	4.7
PM emissions [kg PM10-eq]	4	3.5	2.6
Water Depletion [m3]	1.6	9.4	11.4
Metals Depletion [kg Fe-eq]	0.8	4.3	5.1
Fossils Depletion [kg oil-eq]	2.5	1.3	1

Table 8: Summary of the environmental indicators of two heating systems in a building in the UK for 20 years, adapted from [73]

4. Building envelope solutions

a. Insulation materials

One target of several energy efficiency projects and targets for the decarbonization plans is to improve the building stock's thermal insulation which reduces the energy consumption needed for heating and cooling loads and the environmental impact associated with them, however, the insulation materials used to do it come with their own environmental impact too. An optimization problem arises, that, designers of new constructions or renovation projects should take into consideration to minimize the overall environmental impact of the building, this challenge is very relevant for PROBONO. An article by F. Pittau et al. [74] takes on a case study of industrial buildings in Northern Italy with five materials, conducting a LCA and investigating environmental impact from refurbishment of the building's envelope vs demolition and reconstruction. To allow for comparability, a functional unit of having the same building size with the same thermal insulation.

The results of this study indicate that for refurbishing a building, the more compact materials like Polyurethane (PU) perform better in most indicators as it can be directly installed on the walls of the building without enlarging the volume compared to the bio-based materials like fibre wood (WOOD) and hemp blocks (HEMP). On the other hand, the case of demolition new constructions shows that the integration of organic materials from the design stage is more beneficial and provides a greener solution overall.

If all alternatives are considered in both scenarios, one can see that the refurbishment of old buildings is still more environmentally friendly even when considering the best-case scenario for the demolition phase with recycling. A summary of the GWP of the alternatives can be seen in Figure 9 where the differences, according to the study, is evident and provides a clear overview broken down to the construction phases (Mod A1-5), end-of-life (Mod C), and benefits (Mod D).

Figure 9: The Carbon Footprint (GWP) of five insulation materials in a Refurbishment vs New construction scenarios, adapted from [74]

A review analysis done by S. Schiavoni et al. [75] dives deeper into the commercially available materials in Europe one at a time assessing not only their environmental impact, but their thermal performance and safety in use. The authors gather various LCA studies from literature and group them into ones done in the Cradle-to-Gate (CTGA) approach and others in the Cradle-to-Grave (CTGR) approach that includes the usage and end-of-life stages as well.

The CTGR approach sees less appearances in literature compared to CTGA which is more extensive and can give a good overview of the impacts in terms of Global warming potential (GWP) and embodied energy to produce the materials included in Figure 10. It should be noted that the comparability is allowed since a normalized functional unit has been chosen to account for the mass of material required to achieve the same level of thermal insulation in 1 m2 K/W.

Figure 10: Global warming potential and Embodied energy associated with the production of various building insulation materials, from [76]

As the figure suggests, and coincident with the study mentioned previously, the cellulose-based panels have the lowest GWP and embodied energy. While other more compact materials like XPS and glass fibres perform worse despite having superior performance and resistance to fire.

One other notable study was conducted by N. Llantoy et al. [76] where they set up experimental beds with different insulation materials in Spain. The LCA takes the reference as 1 m² of liveable floor area per year. And they extrapolate the experiment results for 50 years, assuming it's the lifetime of a building. The materials considered are XPS, Polyurethane (PU) and mineral wool. The resulting impacts show higher impacts from XPS, followed by PU and the least is mineral wool. The authors consider the environmental payback period, analogous to economic payback, where they score 12, 15, and 19 years for mineral wool, PU, and XPS respectively. These periods represent the duration after which any savings contribute positively to the lifecycle impacts.

b. Roof solutions

Another sub-segment considered for PROBONO is roof solutions. In the literature, three types of alternative roof solutions are often cited: green roofs (GR) covered with vegetation, white roofs (WR) that reflects sunlight instead of absorbing it, and PV roofs. An article by E. Cubi et al. [77] considers these innovative solutions and their implications in cold climates. The considered functional unit is one large office building in three locations in Canada to study climatic effects.

The authors use different LCA impact indicators to cover for GHG emissions, ecosystem quality, human health, and resource depletion categories. The results are summarized in Figure 11 such that the positive percentage represent reductions in the impacts, and the negative percentages mean the solution is increasing the impact. As can be seen, the white roofs are performing the worst in cold climate because they decrease the solar heat gain during winter, thus increasing the heating load.

Figure 11: Relative environmental impacts of White roofs (WR), Green roofs (GR) and PV roofs considering the upstream embodied impacts and the use phase impacts compared to normal roofs.

Adapted from [77]

Alternatively, in cold climates green roofs (GR) and PV roofs are performing better environmentally in various locations. While PV roofs seem to be performing better in all categories, the authors warn that the climate conditions have a huge impact when comparing the roofs and should be considered case by case to assess the conditions of the green roof as well as the PV production. Another study [78] which compares green roofs (GR) to grey ones display the same evidence that even with extra equipments needed for green roofs, they still perform better environmentally in all indicators along their lifetime.

4.1.2 Techno-economic indicators

The techno-economic indicators include general market outlook to understand the trends and evolution of the market and technological maturity indicators when available. It should be noted that when not available, the indicators may have a different scope (e.g., large scale plants instead of distributed energy generation).

1. Renewable energy generation solutions

There's no doubt that the increased share of renewable energy has a positive environmental impact compared to conventional or non-renewable energy, however, the goal is to compare among the various renewable solutions which ones are performing better and pair that with other constraints to find the most suitable option.

a. Photovoltaic energy

According to the world energy outlook published by IEA [79] the global capacity of installed PV power is expected to grow from 892 to 3020 by the year 2030 according to the STEPS scenario. This 239% increase in capacity is thanks to the technological advancement in the technology and the volume of research that goes into improving the efficiency, prolonging the lifetime of the panels, as well as, reducing the capital cost need to install them. A summary of these indicators has been gathered in Table 9 which highlights the main trends between current status and projections into 2030. Most notably are the economic indicators highlighting a 35% reduction in the capital investment per unit of capacity installed in EU, and a 30% reduction in the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) which makes the technology more appealing economically with the introductions of carbon taxes into the market.

Indicator	2021	2030	Reference
Installed Capacity [GW]	892	3020	[79]
Annual energy generated [TWh]	1003	4011	
Capital cost in EU [\$/kW]	810	530	
LCOE in EU [\$/MWh]	50	35	
Module efficiency [%]	18-22	22-25	[80], [81]
Policy support	Favourable	More favourable	[82], [83]

Table 9: Summary of the techno-economic indicators of the global PV market and trends between 2021 and 2030

Furthermore, the module efficiency can vary greatly based on the material and module type with some new emerging technologies claiming up to 40% efficiency [81] but lacking in scalability and commercialization. It can be concluded that PV technology is very promising in all aspects, and it continues to grow as the leading renewable energy technology for decarbonization with both the economic and technological maturity levels on track to reach global decarbonization goals [84]. A more specific study by H. Gholami and H. N. Rostvik [92] try to assess the LCOE for Building-integrated PV (BIPV) and place it in a positive light as a mature solution in EU context where the authors estimate the average LCOE of BIPV in Europe to be 90 €/MWh compared to the average grid price of 180 deeming it reached grid parity. A main advantage to PV panels is that they are modular, and their scale effect is very small compared to other renewable solutions.

b. Solar thermal (CSP)

The information regarding small scale solar thermal collectors have not been available, therefore the indicators here consider concentrated solar power (CSP) which are often represented by utility scale plants. According to [79], the global installed capacity of CSP is

expected to rise from 7 to 17 GW by the year 2030. And the annual generated energy will increase accordingly. The climatic dependency of the technology has made it receive less attention compared to other renewable solutions and reliable sources about the costs of the plants were limited. A recent study by P. Saini et al. [93] compares parabolic trough (PTC) technology with high temperature heat pumps (HTHP) for industrial applications and conclude that given suitable conditions with high solar irradiance PTC provides lower costs with a levelized cost of heating (LCOH) ranging between 28 to 160 USD/MWh, otherwise, HTHP technology would be considered more suitable economically for steam generation with LCOH between 45 to 130 USD/MWh. The evidence that was collected shows that solar thermal energy should be studied case-by-case as there are high variability in the indicators' values from one region to another. The expected growth is highlighted by [84] in terms of additional collector area growing by 2030 from 729 to 1400 square meters installed.

c. Wind energy

Wind energy is another example of a renewable source that has a strong scale effect, meaning it is receiving little to no attention on small scale applications. According to the world energy outlook [79], the global installed capacity is forecasted to grow from 832 to 1830 GW by 2030. This is more than double the capacity and almost three times the energy generated annually. The outlook [79] has made a distinction between onshore and offshore wind energy as they tend to have different costs based on the civil work required for each of them. A summary of these indicators is found in Table 10. It can be concluded that wind is growing rapidly and is expected, alongside PV, to lead the decarbonization efforts.

Indicator	2021	2030
Installed Capacity [GW]	832	1830
Annual energy generated [TWh]	1870	4604
Onshore Capital cost in EU [\$/kW]	1510	1450
Onshore LCOE in EU [\$/MWh]	50	45
Offshore Capital cost in EU [\$/kW]	2000	1500
Offshore LCOE in EU [\$/MWh]	40	30

Table 10: Summary of the techno-economic indicators of onshore and offshore wind energy between 2021 and 2030 according to [79]

d. Geothermal

According to IEA [79], the global installed capacity of geothermal power is expected to grow from 16 to 28 GW by 2030. And the planned investments are expected to grow [84] from 6 billion USD to 9 billion in the planned energy scenario and 27 billion in accelerated expansions.

Literature has indicated high uncertainty in the economic performance of geothermal power, due to the lack of data and the high level of details required to assess each case. A. Daniilidis et al. [94] approached this problem with a probabilistic model for estimating the LCOE and LCOH for a geothermal project from construction up to 40 years of operation. The resulting indicator shows a mean LCOH of 360 €/MWh_{th} compared to 320 €/MWh_{th} for mature district heating networks, and a reported 630 €/MWh_{th} in the market.

e. Hydropower

While hydropower often means large-scale plants, relevance to PROBONO limits this to small hydro or micro hydro generation. Unfortunately, it's another case in which finding information about the market of small hydro is very limited. One study by R.M. Ciric [95] investigates the techno-economic analysis of a small hydro plant with 600-kW capacity in Serbia. The author concludes that the plant would have a payback period of 36 years with some financial support from the government in the form of feed-in-tariffs, and an annual interest rate of 7%. Another approach was taken by F. J. Lugauer et al. [96] considering a micro-hydro pumped storage plant with speed control. The simulations showed a potential of 42% storage efficiency and a LCOE equal to 860 €/MWh for storage at an interest rate of 6%.

2. Energy storage

a. Batteries

Batteries for utility scale applications have been an object of attention in the plans for decarbonization, often paired with intermittent renewable energy like wind and PV. According to the study by IRENA [87], the installed capacity of batteries is projected to exceed 100 GW by 2030 due to the optimisation of manufacturing and technological advancement.

It also reports some techno-economic indicators for the three main categories of batteries used for utility-scale storage available in the market which are: Lead acid, Lithium-ion, and Flow batteries. A summary of these indicators is provided in Table 11. An overall improvement can be seen in the technology highlighted by the improvement in the efficiency, lifetime of the battery, as well as an economic advantage in the reductions of the installation costs projected into 2030.

	Indicator	2016	2030
Utility scale Li-ion	Energy density [Wh/L]	200-600	200-600
	Roundtrip efficiency [%]	92-96	94-98
	Installation cost [USD/kWh]	200-1260	77-574
	Calendar life up to [years]	20	30
Lead-acid	Energy density [Wh/L]	50-100	50-100
	Roundtrip efficiency [%]	80-82	84-86

	Installation cost [USD/kWh]	105-475	50-240
	Calendar life up to [years]	15	20
Flow batteries	Energy density [Wh/L]	15-70	15-70
	Roundtrip efficiency [%]	70	78
	Installation cost [USD/kWh]	315-1680	108-576
	Calendar life up to [years]	20	30

Table 11: Summary of the techno-economic indicators of the three main types of battery storage for utility scale applications according to [87]

From the technological point of view, another conclusion is evident that lead-acid batteries will be less relevant in the future due to their lower calendar lifetime and the more frequent maintenance required despite their lower capital cost. The valve-regulated type offers little-to-zero maintenance but in turn decrease the lifetime and don't solve the problem of lower efficiency at high ambient temperatures. An alternative represented in flow batteries is seeing a lot of development in recent years. They offer long lifetime and slower aging compared to other types. Flow batteries can also be tailored for specific applications because they enable independent scalability of energy and power. The downside is that they are more expensive due to the need for more auxiliary equipment and sensors for temperature control and proper circulation to avoid acid leakage.

Recent developments in flow batteries have shown that the projections highlighted in Table 12 might not be accurate considering what is being offered in the market now. A techno-economic model was introduced and analysed for several flow battery types by Robert M Darling [86]. The model used aims to find the levelized cost of storage (LCOS) which is defined as the minimum price that investors would require per kWh of electricity stored to break even. It can be seen from Table 12, that in operation, the difference is marginal as flow batteries are catching up to the level of maturity seen in Lithium-ion batteries. When considering current logistic concerns regarding the rare minerals needed for manufacturing Li-ion batteries, it's safe to say that flow batteries is an interesting option for utility scale applications and in grid flexibility.

	Chemistry	Round trip efficiency [%]	Power density [W/cm ²]	Capital cost [\$/kWh]	LCOS [\$/MWh]
Li-ion	LFP	98	0.0032	101	64
Flow batteries	Vanadium redox	81	0.3	173	98
	CrPDTA/Fe(CN) ₆	72	0.23	68	61
	Fe / Cr	67	0.18	92	73
	S / Fe(CN) ₆	62	0.14	93	76
	AQDS / Br	70	0.21	117	81
	S / Br	57	0.19	121	91

	DEBEAQ / Fe(CN) ₆	60	0.17	190	115
	S / Mn	50	0.08	206	130

Table 12: Comparison of techno-economic parameters of flow batteries and Li-ion, according to [86].

b. Thermal energy storage

The market of thermal energy storage is growing rapidly, according to a report by IRENA [88], the global installed capacity of TES is expected to grow from 234 GW in 2019 to 800 GW by 2030. The technology is being used in industrial applications, building sector, and in power systems for load shifting (mainly from CSP). There are several main types of TES including Sensible TES, Latent TES, thermochemical and thermoelectric. When considering use in buildings, only two have reached commercialisation according to [88] sensible and latent TES as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Technological readiness level of Thermal Energy Storage for buildings according to [88]

Focusing on the main types that are commercially available, one can see that the forecasted development is positive in terms of costs, efficiency and lifetime as highlighted in Table 13. Beyond that, operational performance varies between latent and sensible TES according to their energy density, storage period and operating temperature. These indicators are what is used to determine which solution to opt to for the needed application.

	Indicator	2019	2030
Sensible TTES, UTES	Efficiency [%]	55-90	65-90
	Installation cost [USD/kWh]	0.1-35	0.1-25
	Lifetime [years]	10-30	15-30
Latent PCM, Ice	Efficiency [%]	90	92
	Installation cost [USD/kWh]	60-230	45-185
	Lifetime [years]	10	15

Table 13: Summary of the techno-economic indicators of Sensible and Latent Thermal Energy Storage between 2019 and 2030 projections according to [88]

3. HVAC systems

Historically, heating demand has been met by fossil fuels and most of the building stock in cold countries still rely on them. In 2020, around 60% of heating demand in buildings was met by fossil fuels according to IEA [90]. The article also states that the levelized cost of heating (LCOH) is favour of heat pumps due to the reduced running cost, however the households prefer boilers because of lower capital cost. Heat pumps have been considered a cornerstone in the electrification of the heating sector and several reports highlight its capability for offering flexibility service to the grid. A technology report titled “The Future of Heat Pumps” by IEA [89] tackles these topics in detail. They estimate that considering climate change and recent changes in the fossil fuel market and the RePowerEU plan, the global installation and investment in HP will grow substantially in the coming years. A summary of the main findings about that growth can be found in Table 14.

Indicator	2021	2030
Global investment in HP [b\$]	120	350
Global HP installation [GW]	1000	2100
DR potential from HP in EU [GW]	1.5	6.5

Table 14: Market indicators for the installation of Heat Pumps between 2021 and 2030, adapted from [89]

The report also adds that policy changes are needed to push for this transition such that organizations are pushing to ban the production of new fossil fuel heating devices before 2030. When it comes to cooling solutions, the same can be considered since fossil solutions with chillers would offer the same challenges highlighted for heating. In the future, cooling is expected to take more relevance due to the global increase in temperatures due to greenhouse gas emissions. According to [91], the global cooled floor area is expected to grow by 33% and the capacity of cooling by 65% between 2030 and 2022. Heat pumps fit into play as a one solution that could provide both heating and cooling with a small change in the system.

4. Building envelope solutions

Commercialized insulation materials are numerous. They can be categorized according to different criteria based on origin (organic or inorganic), whether they are conventional or unconventional, and advanced materials that offer specific characteristics. S. Schiavoni et al. [97] perform a comparative review and comparative analysis of insulation materials according to their technical and environmental performance. They also provide a description for each of the indicators to facilitate its relevance for insulation materials.

Density of an insulation material is expressed in kg per cubic meters and it's relevant for the thickness of the wall to achieve a specific level of thermal insulation. The less dense a material, the thinner a wall can be while achieving good thermal insulation.

Thermal conductivity represents how well the material allows the heat to pass through it. Consequently, it is the most important indicator that would be considered by the purpose of the material. The lower thermal conductivity is, the better insulation it provides.

Specific heat is expressed in the amount of energy that needs to be absorbed by one kilogram of the material to raise its temperature by one degree. It is relevant for creating a buffer to the outside temperature before it starts heating or cooling. Specific heat also contributes to the thermal mass or inertia of the building envelope which provides flexibility and resilience to the indoor conditions changing.

The last indicator that is more relevant for safety is the material's reaction to **fire classification**. It is according to the European standard EN 13501-1. The letter represents how safe or unsafe is the reaction to fire. A1-A2 for inorganic, non-combustible materials, B to E represent combustible and organic materials ranging from slow combustion to fast. Sound insulation is not analysed in detail in the study; however, the authors highlight that most fibre-based insulation offers good sound absorptivity. Table 15 shows an extract from their extensive table where the most relevant indicators are highlighted for some of the most common insulation materials available in the market.

Material type	Density (kg/m ³)	Thermal conductivity (W/m.K)	Specific heat (kJ/kg.K)	Fire classification
Expanded Polystyrene (EPS)	15-35	0.031-0.038	1.25	E
Extruded Polystyrene (XPS)	32-40	0.032-0.037	1.45-1.7	E
Polyurethane (PU)	15-45	0.022-0.04	1.3-1.4	E
Polyisocyanurate (PIR)	30-45	0.018-0.028	1.3-1.45	B
Stone wool	40-200	0.033-0.04	0.8-1	A1-A2-B
Glass wool	15-75	0.031-0.037	0.9-1	A1-A2
Cellulose	30-80	0.037-0.042	1.3-1.6	B-C-E
Wood fibres	50-270	0.038-0.05	1.9-2.1	E
Mineralized wood fibres	320-600	0.06-0.107	1.8-2.1	B
Hemp blocks	20-90	0.038-0.06	1.6-1.7	E
Cork	110-170	0.037-0.05	1.5-1.7	E
Vacuum insulation panel	160-230	0.0035-0.008	0.8	A1
Aerogel panels	70-150	0.013-0.015	1	C
Recycled textile	30-80	0.036-0.042	1.2-1.6	E, F

Recycled cotton	25-45	0.039-0.044	1.6	E
Recycled glass fibre	450	0.031	1	A1

Table 15: Technical characteristics of some of the commercial insulation materials, adapted from [97]

Economic and cost indicators are more difficult to collect considering that each type of material has more sub-categories under it with several providers and properties. An interesting study to consider was conducted by Schulte et al. [98] where they conduct a life cycle costing (LCC) analysis for high performing insulation materials, and they considered a functional unit to cover 1 m² of wall to reach the same thermal insulation for 70 years. The results from the study are shown in Table 16, and they highlight that the manufacturing costs play the highest role in the totals. The study states that expanded polystyrene outperforms all bio-based materials, despite it performing the worst in almost all environmental impacts.

Life cycle stage	Wood fibre	Hemp fibre	Flax	Miscanthus	EPS	Stone wool
Cultivation	1.51	2.21	2.79	0.9	0	0
Manufacturing	10.33	9.19	6.35	2.76	4.13	8.35
Use phase	0.81	3.7	0.81	3.74	3.7	3.64
End-of-life	1.22	1.31	1.37	1.39	0.46	0.81
Transports	0.37	0.39	0.4	0.41	0.09	0.25
Total [€]	14.24	16.79	11.72	9.18	8.39	13.05

Table 16: Life cycle costing (LCC) of select insulation materials divided into their life stages, from [98]

4.1.3 Social indicators

Incorporating only the techno-economic and environmental aspects does not provide a complete understanding of all the aspects related to particular solutions or technologies. The social and psychological barriers should be taken into consideration from day one of the project's lifetime prioritizing a "problem-first approach". Tackling all the three pillars of sustainability: economic, environmental, and social is key for successful implementation.

It is important to gather social indicators for each solution according to the specific context and circumstances of each project as this plays a major role in how the social indicators are perceived by the stakeholders, and whether they have been involved in the decision-making. The most common social indicators are considered such as job creation, community engagement, quality of life, health benefits, energy accessibility, and social acceptance in general first.

Job creation and economic development assesses the impact of a solution or project on employment opportunities considering various aspects such as 1) direct employment by the project itself, 2) indirect employment through a local economy ripple effect, 3) local employment in which local communities are given priority, 4) economic diversification

stimulating new industries and businesses to expand, and 5) income generation to the community leading to improved living standards and reducing poverty levels.

Community engagement measures how a project involves open and transparent channels for collaborating with local communities and stakeholders. Prioritizing this helps the project implementation to have a close alignment with the specific needs of the stakeholders, as well as contributing to other indicators through the already established communication channels. Community engagement is best included since day one of the planning of the project until the end of the lifetime to ensure long-term sustainability and success.

Quality of life refers to an overall satisfaction and well-being of the individuals affected by the project or solution in various aspects of their lives. This may include physical, mental or health and safety well-being. The approach is human-centric and should be based on social equity, justice, and inclusion. The intertwined nature of the social indicators is highlighted such as quality of life is often affected by and affects stakeholders' engagement and the economic development. A summary of the social indicators' matrix for the PROBONO segments is collected at the end of the section in Table 18.

1. Renewable energy generation solutions

Renewable energy solutions still partially suffer from the false perception that they come with several trade-offs on the economic and social aspect. However, there are socio-economic benefits associated with deployment of renewable energy mainly in terms of employment and welfare on a global scale as well as the local communities.

Energy accessibility was the first social benefit that gets associated with renewable energy, especially for remote under-developed regions where electricity grid infrastructure doesn't exist or is too expensive to extend. Once a region has access to electricity, it gains a lifeline that powers the local economy, communications, health, education, clean water, and irrigation to name a few [99]. The impact is strongly linked to decentralised and modular energy mainly PV and solar thermal applications.

Job creation is another positive aspect related to renewable energy as the sector grows. According to [100] the green energy jobs increased from 7.3 million jobs in 2012, to 13.7 million in 2022. The jobs are divided by technology and are summarised in Table 17. These presented numbers include both direct and indirect employment in the world and in EU27 in the year 2022.

Indicator	Photovoltaic	Solar thermal	Wind energy	Geothermal	Hydropower	Other RE
Global employment	4,902,000	792,000	1,400,000	152,000	2,485,000	3,996,000
EU27 employment	517,000	43,000	319,000	7,000	83,000	565,000

Table 17: Global and European renewable energy employment by technology in 2022, adapted from [100]

The report also highlights some insights into the gender perspective in renewable energy jobs. Solar PV jobs have the highest percentage of women at 40% compared to the average in all renewable energy jobs being 32%. In the context of PROBONO, decentralised buildings and neighbourhood level installations are often community and/or end-user centred. Positive local impacts are often linked directly with generating renewable energy to be self-consumed by the users. **Health benefits** can be associated with the use of clean energy as it replaces burning fuel and therefore the local atmospheric pollution is avoided.

Social Acceptance is dependent on the context of the project, the scale and type of the installation playing a major role. It is important to utilize the community engagement tools to pinpoint and find a common agreement on the installation of renewable energy and innovative solutions.

2. Energy storage

Energy storage is very similar in its socio-economic benefits to renewable energy, whether it is batteries or thermal storage. They both offer *energy accessibility* to local communities and individuals. Energy storage is also considered for *energy security and independence* as it mitigates the variable nature of renewable energy. *Job creation* in the energy storage and renewable energy sector is stimulated by further use of storage solutions both directly and indirectly.

Grid stability and resilience is a special positive impact associated with energy storage as it reduces the strain on the grid and flattens the fluctuations. According to [101], this prevents the need for expensive infrastructure and reduces the risk of a blackout or a brownout. The indirect benefit from grid stability also contributes to the overall welfare of the community.

Energy independence is becoming more desirable by some users in developed areas as well following increased prices of energy and volatility of Time-of-Use pricing. One study about the uptake of storage solutions in Australia [102] suggests that users are willing to invest in batteries to increase their independence. The financial benefits gained from this also contributes to the *social welfare* and an improved *quality of life*.

3. HVAC solutions

Heating and cooling in the buildings sector take up the biggest portion of the energy consumed. It is directly linked to indoor air quality and the thermal comfort of the users. In the context of smart buildings and automation, which is relevant to PROBONO, the human-centred approach to HVAC systems is often cited, especially with a focus on energy efficiency and health. According to [103], proper operation of HVAC improves thermal comfort and indoor air quality which in turn generates a substantial social impact, considering that people spend more than 80% of the time indoors. The main indicators in HVAC solutions are *health and comfort* through proper ventilation and management of the system, *energy affordability* through energy efficiency, and *quality of life* improvement linked to thermal comfort boosting productivity and mental health.

4. Building envelope solutions

Improving the building insulation contributes, like HVAC solutions, to the energy efficiency of the building and reduces the energy demand needed to maintain the thermal comfort which in turn, leads to lower energy prices and improvement in the *welfare* of the occupants placing this in a high regard for *social acceptance*. The renovation wave happening now as a response to the increased energy prices is significantly affecting *job creation* in the building retrofitting sector. According to [104], there are linked positive impacts in *energy equity* and affordability as low-income households get to have lower energy bills, as well as the *community engagement* aspect that has the envelope retrofits being addressed to individuals and their needs rather than the one-solution-fits-all approach. Considering green roof solutions, social and psychological benefits like that of typical green areas have been observed. According to a survey and study conducted by [105] on the use and impact of green roofs on a university campus, most individuals responded positively to indicators such as *social wellbeing* and *place attachment*.

Indicator	Renewable energy	Energy storage	HVAC solutions	Wall insulation	Green roofs
Job creation	x	x		x	x
Quality of life improvement	x	x	x	x	x
Energy accessibility	x	x			
Energy affordability	x		x	x	
Community engagement				x	x
Social acceptance				x	x
Grid stability and resilience		x			
Energy independence	x	x			
Health and comfort	x		x	x	x

Table 18: Social indicators matrix for PROBONO Segments

4.2 Validation of market indicators through interviews

Initially, a total of 6 relevant project partners from consortium and living labs were interviewed. The responses from the interviewees have been documented in this section and anonymity of names has been maintained for privacy purposes. The interviews were conducted through Microsoft Teams and the duration was around 15-30 minutes each. A summary of the most important points discussed is summarised thereafter.

Q1. Introduce yourself and your role within PROBONO.

The first question was intended to get familiar with the interviewees, as well as to let them know about the purpose of the interview and the context of the market analysis presented in this deliverable. Some of the information from this question are utilized and paraphrased within the responses of other questions to provide the viewpoint necessary to understand the answers.

Q2. What do you think of the methodology employed in gathering the indicators?

We presented the interviewees with our methodology highlighted in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Methodology employed in gathering the market indicators.

Most of the interviewees were positive about the methodology as it makes sense and that it is clear. On the positive side, one interviewee highlighted some similarity to a Decision Support System (DSS) they are using in architectural design, however the content within may vary.

“This is similar to our decision support system. We include parameters that would otherwise be omitted in the design process of indoor areas. The focus is to ensure that users are at the centre of the design.” (LL coordinator - AU)

The same interviewee along with another technical provider expressed that some regulatory indicators/effects may be added to the methodology. From their experience, it is relevant for implementation of any innovative solution in public buildings or areas:

“We have already finished the detailed designs and are almost ready for implementation. Yet we still wait for the approval of the local authorities.” (Technical provider 1 - IDOM)

“The studies are ready, and the Living Lab is positive, however the municipality regulations are not suited for upcycling of buildings. It’s not clear how we can satisfy their buildings codes without demolition of the existing buildings.” (Technical provider 2 - COWI)

Q3. Following the same methodology, how would you rate your solution? [Technical partners]

This question was intentionally left open-ended to leave room for the interviewees to share their opinion. Then they are asked if they could rate their solution on the scale of 1 (low) to 5 (high). Some had already done a similar exercise to pitch their idea to the decision makers of an urbanization project.

“We had to propose the advantages to the geothermal-based district heating and cooling system compared to the conventional options. The comparison had implications in the energy efficiency, cost, urban and architectural integration, and possibility to expand in the future. The environmental indicators were implied within the use of geothermal energy, while the social impact was not addressed.” (Technical provider 1 – IDOM)

while others that are more commercial have done their own analysis and studies specific to their own product for specific applications:

“It’s difficult to rate without considerations into the application it will be used in and the size considering the scale effect. Our product shows high superiority to the competitors in terms of CO2 emissions and its recyclability which is supported by studies done within our company.” (Technical provider 3 - VSIB)

On another hand, others were providing a rating for their technology in the market and explaining their reasoning behind the value assigned after being prompted to indicate their opinion in the three categories mentioned in the methodology: techno-economic, environmental, and social:

“I would rate our 2nd life battery system in the techno-economic aspect between 3 and 4 [out of 5 being the best available]; our price is not too high, but you could still find cheaper options in the market too. One would need to consider the performance and the capabilities of EV-grade batteries compared to stationary batteries.”

“In environmental, I think 5/5 is an obvious choice. Second life batteries have a much lower carbon footprint since it is a re-used one, furthermore they reduce the waste that would have occurred had it been landfilled instead.”

“As for the social aspect, I am not sure. We contribute to creating jobs in the community. Our solution may not be accepted by some users due to the bad connotation associated with a “2nd life” product, however batteries in general can have a positive impact and foster community values such as sharing of assets.” (Technical provider 4 – BEEP)

Q4. What do you think of the identified indicators [under the market segment that most closely represent their work or technology/solution]?

In this last question, we showcased the compact version of the indicators collected and explained in detail in section 5.1 and asked their opinion about it whether in general or for a specific segment that is closest to their background and role in PROBONO. As mentioned previously, some have expressed concerns for standardization of the indicators to have a fair comparison under the same assumptions and boundary conditions. Other suggestions came in the form of increasing the level of details in specific segments:

“The insulation performance could differ based on the form they are in, whether in blocks, rolls, or granular form. This should be included to have more information. Also, when it comes to construction materials, the design for reuse and recycling should be included as a stand-alone indicator.” (Technical provider 2 – COWI)

Other feedback came in the form of the need to update and have more relevant information to the current markets. A notable example is in the energy storage segment where innovative solutions are grouped with conventional solutions using the same technology. To that end, the specific solutions employed by PROBONO could be considered on their own using the detailed studies conducted by the developers.

“I think these numbers are exaggerated and not accurate. The costs take a very large range of values leading to a false understanding of the real situation. More recent studies could provide accurate and reliable comparison between Li-Ion and flow batteries. From our internal studies we proved that our solution performs better.” (Technical provider 3 – VISB)

In some cases, there was no segment that aligns with the solution provider such as supporting technologies like sensors and monitoring as a product or service. Therefore, the interviewees had to suggest expanding the indicators to cover for these missing segments.

4.3 Market Indicators summary

The purpose of identifying and collecting the market indicators (Table 19) in relation to the market segmentation done for the GBN technologies and solutions is to provide a comprehensive macro-level understanding of the current and future market trends and scenarios. In addition, the market indicators also provide information about the parameters based on which the technology or solution shall improve and further develop in the future. Interacting with the PROBONO project partners and analysing the interviews provided some useful insights that also helped in developing a common understanding about the segments,

indicators and how these form the basis for formulating the exploitation plans for the key results from the PROBONO project. Thus, the gathered market indicators and the suggestions from the project partners shall be incorporated to have a more tailored approach for the tasks T9.1 and T9.2 going ahead to support the exploitation, replicability, and sustainability strategy. This shall be documented in the PROBONO deliverables D9.3 and D9.4 as per the requirements.

Techno-economic indicators	Environmental indicators	Social indicators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Installed capacity ▪ Annual energy generated ▪ Levelized cost of electricity ▪ Module efficiency ▪ Roundtrip efficiency ▪ Energy/power density ▪ Lifetime ▪ Installation costs ▪ Levelized cost of storage ▪ Investment costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Carbon footprint ▪ Global Warming Potential ▪ Eutrophication Potential ▪ Acidification Potential ▪ Particulate Matter emissions ▪ Freshwater ecotoxicity ▪ Land occupation ▪ Human Toxicity ▪ Greenhouse gas emissions ▪ Metals depletion ▪ Water depletion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Job creation ▪ Quality of life improvement ▪ Energy accessibility ▪ Energy affordability ▪ Community engagement ▪ Social acceptance ▪ Grid stability and resilience ▪ Energy independence ▪ Health and comfort

Table 19: Summary of the Market Indicators

5 Market needs validation towards GBN sustainability

This chapter leverages and follows up the activities already reported in D2.1, D7.1, D8.5 and D9.2 linked to the GBN Innovation Clusters (IC) and the European Ecosystem of GBN Innovation Clusters; within and beyond PROBONO's consortium. By interacting with acknowledgeable stakeholders relevant to the project, from WP9 perspective, this represents an organic follow up that contributes to validate the fundamental insights gathered across project activities. As the title refers to and has just been mentioned, this will contribute to the market needs validation task, as well as the exploitation plans, later during the project when the work starts. Further top-down validation with key representatives of PROBONO's ICs linked to the project's LL and other relevant networks contributing to the establishment of the GBN Ecosystem will be performed later in the project during Task 9.1 and integrated in the project exploitation plan for the results and the LLs. This will enrich further insights interpretation. From the market analysis perspective extensive research has been done on the topic of similar projects and tools therefore a section of this deliverable is focused on mapping relevant innovation clusters on the GBN topic, as well as relevant places where similar projects have been already performed and that can contribute in PROBONO's journey.

5.1 Introduction to PROBONO's market needs validation

PROBONO project covers different dimensions and the work on exploitation of results is tackled from multiple perspective that are required to take into consideration for the activities related to the validation of the market needs. Thus, three dimensions are envisioned:

- Market needs related to the GBN concept – following up the work reported on D9.2 and further presented in this deliverable.
- Market needs related to the ecosystem of GBNs – following up the work reported on D9.2 and further presented in this deliverable.
- Market needs related to PROBONO results – for which trends are presented in the segmentation section of this document, and that will be explored on a tailored basis as part of the business cases discussions for PROBONO's Living Labs and the exploitation plan for every results.

5.2 PROBONO’ solutions customer need validation and links to exploitation plans

5.2.1 GBN Concept market needs validation

The conclusions drawn after PROBONO’s General Assembly Chania workshop¹¹, already described in Deliverable D9.2 can be summarised in the Value Proposition Canvas presented in Figure 14. These conclusions were validated through an on-line questionnaire in order to obtain a broader and more objective view of the external stakeholders. The purpose of this questionnaire was to rank the customer profile items obtained through the “Value Proposition Canvas”.

Figure 14: Customer profile of decision makers for GBN deployment in local ecosystems (urban planners and other related roles).

The questionnaire for the market needs validation was launched among the **onboarded** PROBONO Living Labs and also among the **key representatives** from Sister projects and the Advisory Board members during the meeting held on Friday 24th November. The link to the questionnaire is available here: [reference](#), which header is presented in the following figure:

Figure 15: PROBONO questionnaire on market needs validation of the GBN concept.

The results obtained were scored by the participants according to the importance of the results, being the final benchmark displayed as follows:

¹¹ PROBONO’s first physical General Assembly took place in Chania, Greece in February 2023. The workshop focused on progressing on the GBN definition with the involvement of all the project consortium. As part of the workshop a dedicated session took place in order to define the need and the added value of the GBN concept, by using the Value Proposition Canvas as a main tool

QUESTION 1: CURRENT RESPONSIBILITIES

1. Renovation of existing assets of the built environment at different levels.
2. Installation of renewable energy production and reduce dependency on non-renewable sources.
3. Procurement and tendering of solutions
4. Education of stakeholders and awareness creation on sustainability needs.
5. Consider current and future usage of buildings and infrastructures and provide flexibility.
6. Increased Quality of Life.

QUESTION 2: PAINS

1. Lack of funding for green transition and attraction of investors.
2. High complexity of the local and regional environments.
3. Lack of technical expertise.
4. Short term political interests.
5. High costs of green transition.
6. Disrupted management of data across built environment lifecycle (design, construction, operation).
7. Lack of stakeholder engagement

QUESTION 3: GAINS

1. Integrate all dimensions of sustainability in decision making.
2. Climate change proofing of infrastructures.
3. Improved circularity and reduced primary resources consumption and environmental impact.
4. Reduced risk in high technology investment and deployment.
5. Increased attractiveness and value of the local environment and its assets.
6. Common rules for the long term and better decision making.
7. Eased tendering processes.
8. Cohesive LCA based on norms and standards.

Other additional comments included in the questionnaire: *“Awareness of and access to green finance is a key issue. What is largely overlooked is well are the social (and ecological) co-benefits of GBNs (or SPENs/PENs/PEDs) as recognised in certification systems such as BREEAM”*. This information will be taken into account when designing the exploitation routes of PROBONO’s GBN concept and all PROBONO’s results in general.

5.2.2 Pathway to validate PROBONO’s commercial and competitive advantage as part of Living Labs Business Cases

PROBONO has defined a pathway to integrate and validate further the GBN concept by integrating it in a business case that will be developed for each living lab and in joint collaboration with the LL’s innovation clusters as referred in D9.2. As presented in the already mentioned D9.2, the business case for the LLs will rely on the ‘five case model’ methodology, that covers the dimensions that shall be able to respond the questions that are presented in Table 20 below:

Strategic case	Is the GBN needed? Is there a clear definition of what is expected to be achieved?
Economic case	Is the GBN best value for money solution when considering all the costs and benefits? Has a sensitivity analysis been carried out?
Commercial case	Is the GBN technically viable? Is PROBONO ER’s Business Model viable?

Financial case	Have cost of the transition been quantified? Is the funding model of the GBN structured?
Management case	Is the GBN achievable with the stakeholder involved? Is the Innovation Cluster (IC) clearly identified and organised?

Table 20: Five cases model preliminary assessment for PROBONO's LLs

As can be seen in Table 20, ‘commercial case’ assessment will allow a seamless integration of the exploration of LL/GBN sustainability in the 6 PROBONO pilots, with the validation of PROBONO’s ERs value proposition. Business Case discussions will start in Q1 2025 (project’s M24-M26) and will pave the way for the creation of the first exploitation plan of projects results by the end of the year, reported in D9.3.

5.3 Innovation clusters identification

In the framework of the PROBONO project, 2 lighthouse and 4 follower Living Labs (LLs) have been established in order to test and validate the broad pool of solutions that are represented by the different market segments presented in chapter 3 of this analysis. LLs sustainability pathway will be discussed as part of PROBONO’s exploitation strategy. However, in parallel, LLs also represent an environment for testing and validating the GBN concept. As discussed in publicly available deliverable D9.2, the exploitation and sustainability pathways for the GBN concept is represented and summarised by the following layers:

Figure 16: Pathway to GBN concept exploitation and sustainability from PROBONO's LLs

LLs, GBNs and GBNs Innovation Clusters (layers 1 to 3 from left to right in Figure 16), are context relative to the local ecosystems that are planning or being transformed to become a GBN or future GBNs. Thus, this analysis focuses on the key stakeholders, more specifically relevant Innovation Clusters as sectorial networks across Europe that are expected to enable the creation of a European ecosystem of GBN Innovation Clusters (GBN ecosystem for short).

5.3.1 European ecosystem of GBN Innovation Clusters

The GBN ecosystem is defined as a network that builds on the work of the project to form alliances beyond the LL of the project and PROBONO consortium as a whole. The main activities of the GBN ecosystem will be:

- External collaborations maximise the visibility and impact of the project.
- Ensures cohesion between different local and regional environments.

PROBONO is proactively leading the creation of the ecosystem or the integration of the proposed approach within other relevant networks. Market needs validation has also focused on the GBN ecosystem with selected actors within and beyond the consortium.

5.3.2 Innovation Clusters and other relevant networks identified

5.3.2.1 Identification of Innovation Clusters

Existing Innovation Clusters (that were already referred in D9.2) are multiplier actors that can support the establishment of the GBN Ecosystem, given their capacity to represent multiple stakeholder interests and their knowledge of ongoing national to regional initiatives in their respective countries.

A preliminary version of the Innovation clusters identified is attached in Annex 1 on which the most active clusters have been marked **in bold**. The list was performed by partner CGBC, that represents one of the multipliers networks PROBONO targets with the GBN Ecosystem vision.

Figure 17: Innovation clusters geographical coverage (numbers represent number of active IC).

It is also observed in Figure 17 that innovation clusters cover almost the whole European Union, meaning that a good network for sharing the knowledge should be established. Nevertheless, a good geographical coverage of clusters does not imply the establishment of good communication channels that allows the exchange of experiences, good practices and synergies among the relevant stakeholders. It is remarkable the case of Spain, where 14 innovation clusters have been formed that may overlap in their main activities. For that reason, a good identification of the most representative clusters in relation with PROBONO, has being developed in order to create an accurate environment for the GBNs.

5.3.2.2 Preliminary map of other relevant initiatives and networks

This section refers to actual relationships and events in which PROBONO is involved and that are effectively contributing to the project measures to maximise impact and will be linked to the establishment of the GBN Ecosystem, also linked to PROBONO's liaison activities under WP8.

PROBONO has initiated interactions towards the establishment or integration of the envisioned GBN Ecosystem. It is important to mention here PROBONO's sister projects: ARV and oPEN LAB, with which recurrent and fluent communication has been established. Besides, and as presented in the report on liaison activities, PROBONO is part of the 'Smart Energy Cluster'. Moreover, significant other EU funded projects have also been identified by using PNO's proprietary tool WheesBee, as presented below:

1. *Neighbourhood and infrastructures planning and regeneration*: ECOLOPES (H2020), RethinkAction (H2020), MAKING-CITY (H2020), INSULAE (H2020), frESCO (HORIZON).
2. *Multi-stakeholder participation and behavioural change*: SPARCs (H2020), WaysTUP! (H2020), NGI4ALL.E (H2020), TANDEMS (LIFE), SENDER (HORIZON), ACCEPT (H2020), ENCHANT (HORIZON).
3. *Resources efficiency in the built environment*: ATELIER (H2020), zEPHYR (H2020), Smart Circular Bridge (SCB) (Interreg), SASEC (Interreg), CHRONICLE (HORIZON), SYN-IKIA (H2020), EXCESS (H2020), POCITYF (H2020), SPARCs (H2020), DE-RISK (HORIZON).
4. *Digitalisation*: REGFUT (H2020), PRODIGEEES (H2020), DIGIPLAN (Interreg), BIM2TWIN (H2020), INTERCONNECT (H2020), TWINERGY (HORIZON), CHRONICLE (HORIZON), PRECEPT (H2020).
5. *Smart growth*: SmartSPIN (H2020), DROP (HORIZON), SUPERSHINE (H2020), JUSTNature (H2020), CitizEE (H2020).
6. *Accessibility and inclusivity*: DivAirCity (H2020), IDR TOOLKIT (H2020), SYNERGIES (H2020).
7. *Sustainable lifestyles and business models*: PSLifestyles (H2020), GreenNexUS (HORIZON).

Furthermore, PROBONO is part of the **Urban Environment and Mobility working group**, participating in the last meeting held on 1st of December together with other Green Deal funded projects (including the sister projects), also linked with the Fit for 55 package. The main actions planned for this working group are to investigate common implications from Fit for 55 and coordinate common influence on policy makers.

Figure 18: 4th Urban Environment and Mobility working group meeting (December 1st, 2023).

Finally, PROBONO has also established contacts with other initiatives for the sake of the validation of stakeholder needs with different dimensions of the project (GBN concept, Ecosystem of GBNs and exploitable results). The links with the Advisory Board and other direct or indirect relationships with networks like Built4People NEBULA ([reference](#)), EERA Joint Programme on Smart Cities ([reference](#)) or Spanish Network of Smart Cities ([reference](#)).

5.3.3 PROBONO's relationship towards the creation of the GBN ecosystem

In order to understand the added value of proposed PROBONO's GBN ecosystem towards the actors mapped in the previous section, two main exercises have been performed and are presented in this section:

- First, an analysis of the vision, the mission and the value proposition of the GBN ecosystem.
- Second, a SWOT analysis to understand what PROBONO relationship towards all these actors is and how to tackle the relationship between the project and other relevant networks.

5.3.3.1 PROBONO GBN Ecosystem vision, mission and value proposition

Based on the preliminary findings so far (presented in D9.2), the vision, the mission and the value proposition are presented below:

- **The vision:** To emerge as a single-entry point for sustainable local and regional ecosystems, in which sustainability and innovation are mainstreamed to all stakeholders that can belong or contribute to the innovation cluster than can effectively achieve the GBN in all these local environments.
- **The mission:** To deliver guidance, tools and showcase success stories to all stakeholders willing to contribute to make the built environment more sustainable, also including the dialogue across multiple groups in order to facilitate scenarios planning to benefit all citizens and stakeholders.
- **The value proposition:** To mainstream sustainability through clear pathways that rely on objective decision making towards matching needs and expectations across different stakeholder groups. To enhance quality of life and wellbeing of all stakeholders, including accessibility, inclusiveness and prosperity.

5.3.3.2 PROBONO GBN Ecosystem SWOT analysis

Table 21 below illustrates a preliminary SWOT analysis performed to understand the position of the GBN ecosystem towards the actors that shall contribute to its further definition and establishment or integration across Europe and globally. This will be refined as the discussion with the multiple stakeholders take place.

Internal factors - strengths
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One-stop-shop for green neighbourhoods. • Cohesive and evidence-based concepts implementing standards and certificates.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systemic innovations for neighbourhoods (from social to technical). • Effective and multidisciplinary participation. • Supported by the PROBONO project and aligned with other
Internal factors – weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All proposed concepts shall be anyways tailored to the local or regional reality. • PROBONO as such will be unable to monitor or follow up all the potential cases after the project if no additional resources or commitment are secured also due to the long-lasting transformation processes that greening a complex neighbourhood may require.
External factors - Opportunities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current context leading to major changes in the built environment towards achieving ambitious climate goals. • Fast growing population in condensed urban ecosystems. • Integrated sustainability principles are a central pillar for major projects and initiative.
External factors - Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extremely atomised targeted audience with no clear responsible besides urban planners. • Legacy initiatives no longer active with no clear responsible either. • Ineffective collaboration. • Imbalances between sustainability, prosperity, inclusiveness, accessibility and personal motivations and expectations.

Table 21: PROBONO's GBN ecosystem SWOT assessment.

5.3.4 Plan for stakeholder validation and onboarding

As mentioned in sections 5.3.2.1 and 5.3.2.2, as part of PROBONO's liaison activities, PROBONO has already established strong links with relevant projects and networks and initiatives. However, the work for onboarding stakeholders from the different layers that affect the project are subject to exploitation planning strategy, as mentioned in section 5.2.2. Thus, the different stakeholder groups will be involved as follows:

- LL related stakeholders forming PROBONO's GBN Innovation Clusters – are expected to be part of M24 to M26 activities to define the Business Cases of the project LLs as key representatives onboarded to project activities. This does not preclude that other activities may be executed later within the project, as far as the value proposition of PROBONO's results is clearly matched within the Business Cases.
- Stakeholders relevant to the definition, establishment and sustainability assessment of the GBN ecosystem have already been involved for the sake of the questionnaire which results are presented in this document. This will be further expanded due to the participation of PROBONO in relevant events late in the moment this document has been elaborated, like the Smart City Expo World Congress in Barcelona or the ENLIT Conference in Paris, both events taking place in November 2023.

6 PESTLE Analysis and Innovation Potential to Market

6.1 PROBONO PESTEL Analysis focused on KIR deployment to the market

PESTEL analysis is a tool that organizations traditionally use in market-focused strategic planning. The main objective is to examine the business environment in which an organization operates and identify the key Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal factors that could impact the organization. The PESTEL model is not a new concept but a combination of several other models and research works from the related market analysis literature. Initially, the PEST model [107] and STEPE model [108] were introduced, and later, the ETPS model [109], created by Francis Aguilar, introduced Environmental dimensions, forming the STEPE model. Finally, the Legal Environment was eventually added by several researchers, leading to the widely accepted PESTEL analysis framework.

In that context, the current PESTEL analysis aims to serve as a macro-level influences assessment for the innovation potential to market that PROBONO outcomes are expected to bring to GBN markets after the project's lifetime. It is conducted under Subtask 9.1.3 and aims to provide the background for analysing two Key Innovative Results (KIRs) of the project in later sections of this report.

In connection to the PESTEL analysis of WP1 and D1.7 that focuses on the Brussels LL and the GBN implementation aspect, this WP9 PESTEL analysis is focused on the factors that affect the deployment of innovative artefacts of PROBONO to the GBN markets. One can view the PESTEL analysis of D9.1 and WP9 as an extension to the PESTEL analysis of WP1 and D1.7. Several PESTEL factors, or macro-level influences as usually referenced in scientific literature, are common between the two PESTEL analyses of WP1 and WP9: In the Political Factors, this report draws insights from D1.7 and further augments the belief that the Paris Agreement and the Fit-for-55 package are two of the most important political initiatives that will affect the deployment of products and services to markets. In the same way, regarding the economic macro-level influences, GDP per capita/inhabitant has been considered an important indicator. Still, in the ST9.1.3 case, the global economic outlook is considered in the long term for the further development and deployment of outcomes. In the social aspect, the current PESTEL is further augmented to include the population ageing as an important factor connecting to economic prosperity, as well as R&D expenditure, which is expected to be an important influence for the further development of innovative outcomes of PROBONO. In the technological aspect, several key technologies are included in this report that are expected to shape products and services in

GBNs. One example is Narrowband IoT (NB-IoT) technology, which, when supported by 5G technology [110], can enable denser sensor networks in buildings and neighbourhoods, which can further support monitoring functions of ICT platforms. In the legal framework influences, while in both D1.7 PESTEL and D9.1 PESTEL, construction laws and standards are included as highly impactful areas, but in this extension, the legislative framework around net metering and feed-in tariff policies, as well as EU's IP Protection legislation are considered as important factors. Similar to Figure 3 of PROBONO's deliverable D1.7, an overview of the D9.1 PESTEL analysis is given in Figure 19 below:

Figure 19: PESTEL analysis' macro-level influences considered inspired by PROBONO's D1.7's Figure 3

While there are several things in common between the two analyses, there are also differences. In the technological aspect, D1.7 PESTEL analyses the data management and collection procedures as a critical factor in Digital Twin development. In this D9.1 PESTEL analysis, this factor is considered not important at the macro-level since investments in technologies, such as a DT Platform, usually take place after a technology reaches higher maturity levels. Data availability and collection is generally an issue in lower technological readiness levels and research tasks that aim to prototype a solution. In addition to the analysis of Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal factors, for the T9.1 PESTEL, an analysis of recent disruptive phenomena, the COVID-19 pandemic and the War in Ukraine is included. Since this phenomenon occurred over the last four years, several negative effects have appeared for economic, R&D expenditure and the energy sector in Europe. At the end of this PESTEL analysis, and in connection to PROBONO's deliverable report D1.7, an overall presentation of the factors' significance is given.

6.1.1 Political factors

Government policies and regulations can significantly influence the adoption of innovative products in GBN-related markets. The stability of the political environment and the government's willingness to promote sustainable development can encourage the use of innovative products. On the other hand, political instability, bureaucratic hurdles, and conflicting regulations can hinder the adoption of innovative products. For example, the government can incentivize the use of renewable energy, green mobility, and sustainable materials by providing tax credits and subsidies, thereby promoting the adoption of innovative products. Furthermore, clear policies and regulations that are not contradicting each other can further support energy-efficient buildings and sustainable infrastructure, making it easy for investors to adopt new green technologies in old building infrastructure.

In the European context, the participation of outcome owners' home countries in the European Economic Area (EEA), Eurozone (E.Z.), and Schengen Convention (S.C.) can be beneficial for innovative outcomes. Through the EEA and E.Z. memberships, outcome owners can participate in cross-country contracts more easily, reducing bureaucracy, negotiations, and contracts. Additionally, innovative outcomes related to PROBONO can expect to benefit from the European Union (E.U.) and European Commission's (E.C.) actions towards achieving the European Green Deal, which aims to achieve zero net emissions of Greenhouse Gases (GHG) by 2050.

Given the EC's commitment to environmental protection through the Green Deal and the Fit-For-55 packages, maintaining policy coherence and implementing long-term planning can be expected to be crucial in fostering investments in Green Building Neighbourhoods. A stable political environment and a steadfast dedication to sustainability objectives can instil developers with the assurance needed to invest in forward-looking, innovative endeavours. Under that framework, government funding, grants, tax incentives, and subsidies can significantly influence developers' investment decisions in green building innovations. Political willingness to allocate resources towards sustainable initiatives in the long-term can encourage private sector participation despite fluctuations in the economic performance of the different EU MS and respective regions and organizations.

6.1.2 Economic factors

This section focuses on two important economic factors that will impact PROBONO's outcomes, namely the research and development (R&D) expenditure of European Union member states and the overall economic status of the world, particularly that of European countries. The

literature has extensively studied the relationship between the economy's performance and R&D expenditure, and it is widely accepted that both factors impact each other and the adoption of innovative products and services [111]. In the case of GBN innovative outcomes and related applications, this is no different, where the R&D expenditure in EU countries is expected to either positively or negatively influence the deployment of PROBONO's outcomes to the intended target groups. This is especially true for outcomes that aim to further utilize R&D projects for developing the outcomes.

Figure 20: Gross domestic expenditure on R&D from 2010 to 2020. This is based on data from the E.U. commission's Eurostat [112].

In recent years, there has been consistent or increased R&D expenditure, as shown in Figure 20. While Japan and the United States have a leading role with higher R&D expenditures, the EU has recently increased its average R&D expenditure, showcasing positive signs. Despite this fact, the overall economic performance of many countries has not been as stable. There are now concerns about the challenges that EU MS face, such as the ongoing conflict in Ukraine and the reliance on Russian energy imports. This situation is further compounded by the sanctions imposed by European countries and the US on Russia, which may lead to severed relationships and decreased collaboration between countries. The result could be higher energy prices, which, as commonly discussed [113], could have far-reaching effects on various economic sectors and have implications for decades to come.

While R&D spending has remained stable or increased in recent years, the same cannot be said for the overall economic performance of numerous nations. Ongoing events, such as the conflict in Ukraine and Europe's reliance on Russian energy imports, have presented formidable challenges for European Union member states. Furthermore, the implementation of sanctions by both European nations and the United States against Russia has exacerbated this situation, potentially leading to strained international relationships and diminished collaboration.

Consequently, there exists a significant risk of heightened energy costs, which, as discussed above [113], have the potential to influence a range of economic sectors and exert long-term effects spanning decades. The graphical representation in Figure 21 presents an indicator, the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), of the EU over the past fifty years.

Figure 21: EU's Gross Domestic Product in Trillion United States Dollars (USD) from 1970 to 2020. Based on data from the World Bank¹²

Finally, and as mentioned in PROBONO's D1.7, it is worthwhile to refer to the GDP per capita metric in the EU. GDP per capita is considered a very important factor for the long-term development of individuals within the specified area [114]. It is expected that this may affect education, which in turn can affect the long-term perception of innovation and connected technological or technical artefacts that may be adopted by markets and further improve the quality of life. For that reason, it is important to monitor GDP per capita and, as stated in D1.7 PESTEL analysis, be aware of potential risks that climate change may bring (and potential decreases within specific affected areas).

6.1.3 Social influences

The adoption of innovative products in GBN-related markets can be influenced by sociocultural factors such as consumer preferences, social values, and cultural norms. If consumers are aware of environmental issues and climate change, they may be more likely to adopt innovative products that promote sustainability. Conversely, if there is a lack of awareness and resistance to change, it can slow down the adoption of PROBONO's innovative products. Furthermore,

¹² The World Bank DataBank website, GDP (current US\$) - European Union, Link: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.CD?locations=EU>

demographic trends, such as the increasing urban population, can influence the demand for GBNs and the adoption of innovative products.

According to data from the World Bank [115], the population of the EU has been steadily increasing from 356 million in 1960 to 447 million in 2020. While population growth can be a positive sign for long-term economic development [116], the growth rate has been steadily declining since the 1960s. Another factor to consider is the ageing of the population, which has been linked to potential decreases in productivity in the EU [117]. The EU's population pyramid is an interesting tool to consider in this discussion of ageing populations, as shown in Figure 22.

Figure 22: The E.U.'s population pyramid, describing the distribution of the percentage of each age from 0 to 100+ for men and women for 2019 and 2100 (estimation). Source: Eurostat's Glossary [30]

Based on Figure 22, one can notice that E.U.'s elderly population is estimated to vastly increase over the years, with the working-age group being expected to be narrowed down considerably. This phenomenon can be expected to affect GBNs and urban environments, but effects will likely show in the long-term. This means that outcome owners do not necessarily need to expect their outcomes to be affected but probably must account for this longer-term effect.

The sociocultural factors described above are mainly expected to affect the deployment of Innovative and Exploitable results in the long term. Recent developments have shown that these factors may be further complicated by external issues, such as the war in Ukraine and the EU's dependency on Russian energy imports. Sanctions imposed on Russia by the EU and the US may lead to a breakdown in relationships between countries and reduced collaboration, which can

possibly lead to higher energy prices, affecting various economic sectors over long periods of time.

6.1.4 Technological factors

Further advancements in technology can be expected to greatly affect PROBONO innovations deployment to market in both good and bad ways. On the one hand, the advancement of technology can support innovative outcomes for owners to further develop features of products and services and address market's needs, or on the other hand, advancements may make PROBONO innovations less competitive in markets.

Overall, there are several technological factors at the macro-level that can affect the implementation of GBN innovations in European markets in the near future. The growing prevalence of digital technologies combined with physical systems (i.e., cyber-physical systems) can improve the capabilities of GBN innovations, leading to more efficient use of resources. The deployment of 5G and 6G networks is also expected to accelerate the growth of GBN applications such as smart cities and autonomous vehicles. However, potential cybersecurity threats and the risk of data privacy breaches may impede the acceptance of these technologies as consumers become more wary of the associated risks of connected devices.

The development of renewable energy technologies is central to establishing GBNs and the broader macro-level factors influencing them. These state-of-the-art technologies, encompassing solar panels, wind turbines, and energy-efficient systems, have fundamentally transformed our approach to powering and constructing communities. By harnessing these renewable energy sources, GBNs can significantly diminish their dependence on fossil fuels, mitigate greenhouse gas emissions, and bolster overall sustainability. For example, solar panels empower these neighbourhoods to generate clean electricity, reducing energy expenses and a decreased environmental footprint. Furthermore, advancing efficient energy storage solutions guarantees a consistent power supply, even during fluctuations in renewable energy production, thereby strengthening energy resilience. Essentially, the continuous evolution of renewable technology empowers GBNs to pioneer environmental stewardship and energy efficiency. These technological innovations not only align with the global imperative to combat climate change but also elevate the residents' quality of life, rendering green neighbourhoods more appealing and sustainable places to reside. Special emphasis should be applied to hydrogen-utilization technologies, which promise to bring innovative effects to the way we live.

Figure 23: Main expected technological macro-level influences for the deployment of PROBONO outcomes to GBN-related markets

To conclude, there are various macro-level factors that can influence the deployment of ICT, scientific modelling, and DT-related innovations (Figure 23). The integration of digital technologies with physical systems can improve the effectiveness and efficiency of GBN innovations, aided by the development and deployment of 5G and 6G networks. The growing availability of data in the GBN context due to the increasing digitalization of the sector and the use of IoT-centric applications, such as Narrowband IoT (NB-IoT), can provide a suitable platform for smart energy management applications. With the use of technologies like RFID, 5G, and NB-IoT, larger volumes and diverse types of data can be collected and analysed to support decision-making outcomes in the PROBONO project. However, cybersecurity threats and data privacy concerns could impede the adoption of connected devices. Additionally, the availability of key resources, such as rare earth metals and battery technology, and concerns over their ethical and environmental impacts may drive demand for alternatives or more sustainable extraction methods.

6.1.5 Environmental influences

Environmental factors such as climate change, environmental degradation, and natural disasters can play a significant role in adopting innovative products in GBN markets. The increasing concerns over environmental degradation and climate change can promote the adoption of innovative products that promote sustainability and minimize environmental impact. Additionally, the frequent occurrence of natural disasters can create a demand for resilient infrastructure and GBNs that can withstand these challenges.

Degradation of air and water quality is also a major impact in cities that may create room for PROBONO outcomes in markets. The rapid expansion of cities often comes at the expense of deforestation and the loss of green spaces, which are needed to make room for infrastructure development, disrupting ecosystems and reducing biodiversity. This loss of natural habitats contributes to the degradation of the environment and exacerbates the effects of climate

change. Related to this are waste management strategies and waste management systems, which can help tackle the increasing waste problems. Additionally, cities can implement comprehensive strategies prioritizing recycling, composting, and proper disposal. Promoting citizen participation through awareness campaigns and providing adequate waste collection infrastructure can significantly reduce waste pollution.

Moreover, the accessibility of crucial resources such as rare earth metals and battery technology materials could also influence the development and implementation of GBN innovations. Concerns over the ethical and environmental impacts of mining these resources may stimulate the demand for alternatives or more sustainable extraction methods. Also connected to the supply chain risks that emerged from the COVID-19 pandemic and the War in Ukraine, the potential scarcity of rare earth metals in the future poses significant challenges for GBNs, which prioritize sustainability and environmental friendliness. GBNs rely on advanced technologies containing rare earth elements, such as wind turbines, solar panels, and energy-efficient lighting for renewable energy projects. A shortage of these elements could raise costs and delay green energy initiatives, hindering carbon reduction goals. Finally, electric vehicles (EVs) are essential in GBNs for emission reduction, but their motors and batteries depend on rare earth materials. A future scarcity could impede EV deployment, slowing down sustainable mobility efforts. Additionally, GBNs use advanced technologies like smart grids and energy-efficient windows, often incorporating rare earth elements. Shortages may limit the adoption of these eco-friendly solutions, jeopardizing overall sustainability objectives. Addressing rare earth scarcity in GBNs necessitates strategic planning, including diversifying supply chains, promoting recycling, and researching alternative materials. Without proactive measures, the development and success of GBNs, crucial for sustainable urban living, could face substantial challenges due to future rare earth shortages.

As discussed in WP1's PESTEL analysis, the emergence of heatwaves and the creation of heat islands can impede the progress of GBNs through increased energy use (for cooling needs), altered urban planning, jeopardized sustainability aims and overall adverse effects on residents' well-being. Other effects can be pressure on water resources (such as small lakes and water reservoirs), green space and parks degradation, and the need for costly climate adaptation measures (such as low emissions zones from transport operations). To address these challenges, GBN developers and urban planners must prioritize climate-resilient design, incorporate effective cooling tactics, and account for local climate conditions. This includes considering

options like heat-reflective materials, green roofs, and shade trees to uphold GBNs' sustainability goals while mitigating extreme heat impacts.

As environmental pressures continue to increase, stakeholders in GBNs, such as building managers, owners, and local authorities, will require tools to monitor and reduce the impact of their operations. The PROBONO project outcomes provide decision-making support for such stakeholders, and there is an expectation that the demand for such tools will increase in the coming years.

6.1.6 Legal influences

The legal and regulatory framework can significantly influence the adoption of innovative products in GBN-related markets. The E.U. tends to adopt a shared approach to coordinate and cooperate between countries when applying new technological standards in real-world settings. Regulations and laws related to sustainability and green development, such as those resulting from the European Green Deal, can promote the adoption of innovative products. The Green Deal aims to achieve zero net emissions of greenhouse gases by 2050, and several legislative actions are expected to be released by the E.C. to stop climate change and solve environmental problems. In the bigger picture, legal factors can support or discourage industries and technologies, affecting their adoption. Legal factors such as sustainability regulations and laws can “force” organizations and GBNs to apply certain standards and significantly impact the adoption of innovative products in GBN-related markets.

In alignment with the Green Deal and as referenced in D1.7 PESTEL, construction laws, building codes, and standards define the minimum requirements for energy efficiency, water conservation, and sustainable practices. These guidelines serve as a blueprint for architects, builders, and developers, encouraging the integration of technologies that drive sustainability and energy efficiency. Additionally, simplifying the permitting and approval processes for GBN projects (through building codes and standards) and incorporating innovative technologies reduce barriers and foster adoption. One example is streamlining administrative procedures; developers can navigate the complex regulatory landscape more efficiently.

The legislative framework around net metering and feed-in tariff policies can also provide attractive financial incentives for incorporating renewable energy systems in GBNs. Net metering enables GBNs to sell excess energy generated by renewable technologies back to the grid, while feed-in tariffs guarantee payments for renewable energy generation. These

mechanisms create economic opportunities that encourage the implementation of solar panels, wind turbines, and other renewable energy solutions within GBNs.

Finally, connected to Task 9.3 and the IP and IPR Protection Methodology, as presented in D9.5, safeguarding intellectual property rights is crucial for promoting innovation and technology development in the GBN sector. The legal framework ensures that intellectual property is protected, giving technology providers the confidence to invest in research and development and bring new solutions to the market. In addition, data privacy and security regulations address concerns associated with data collection and interconnected systems in GBNs. By establishing clear guidelines on data sharing, consent, and storage, the legal framework promotes responsible and secure technology implementation in GBNs, fostering trust and confidence among stakeholders.

6.1.7 The Effect of the COVID-19 Pandemic and the War in Ukraine

The COVID-19 pandemic and the War in Ukraine are two macro-level events that can potentially influence the deployment of GBN innovations in European markets. Therefore, the current PESTEL analysis is extended to include these two effects since they are expected to affect the development and deployment of PROBONO results after the project's lifetime. Starting with the COVID-19 pandemic, the crisis has caused a major disruption to the global economy, affecting many industries and supply chains. The industries and domains comprising the GBN market, such as construction, energy and technology sectors. Especially during the initial face of the pandemic, supply chain disruptions [118], reduced demand, and border closures have all impacted the movement of goods and people, resulting in increased demand for digital solutions and innovations that can facilitate remote work and contactless delivery.

On the other hand, the pandemic has also highlighted the potential risks associated with digital technologies, especially in SMEs [119]. Cybersecurity threats have increased as more people work remotely and rely on digital systems, while concerns around data privacy and protection have also grown. These risks may create barriers to adopting GBN innovations, particularly in sectors where security and privacy are critical, such as healthcare and finance.

In 2023, after the global vaccine development and distribution period, it is considered that the global recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic is still ongoing across many sectors. While this recovery is uneven between the different parts of the world, the spread of the virus is considered to be under control. While this phenomenon has impacted European countries in mostly negative ways, especially when one considers the economic effects and mental

challenges to the population, it has been considered to kickstart a digital transformation for a lot of companies [120]. As expected, while economic activity has been reduced during the COVID-19 pandemic, with several countries' economies being severely damaged, technological innovation in some sectors has been one of the few benefits [121].

Turning to the War in Ukraine, starting in February 2022, with the European and global economy being shocked by the COVID-19 pandemic, the geopolitical tensions emerging from the conflict in Ukraine came to disrupt global affairs further. The great uncertainties in energy markets caused by the concerns over the stability and reliability of gas transit routes brought geopolitical tensions, which were further augmented by the sanctions imposed on Russia by the global community. Especially focusing on the energy sector, given the reliance of Europe on Russian gas has been of great importance over the past few decades [122], the EU's plans [123] to reduce energy reliance on Russia are expected to positively affect the deployment of innovative outcomes across all the domains of PROBONO's outcomes. With the latest positive signs in the decrease of energy prices over the third quarter of 2023, energy security concerns in Europe are also expected not to significantly affect the energy markets. In addition to that, and as discussed in the analysis of D1.7, the rising energy costs may not only affect PROBONO's results deployment in the long term, but it may also impede adoption in the short term. As included in the WP1 PESTEL, changes in energy prices may affect partners' projections about energy savings and reduction of costs, which may affect business cases for project outcomes and the perception of their value by potential investors or the management boards within companies.

Other substantial impacts are connected to the supply of key computer hardware components and materials [124], as Ukraine is a major producer of critical minerals such as titanium, zirconium, and iron ore. Any disruption to these supply chains could have a significant impact on the availability and cost of these materials, potentially slowing down the development and deployment of GBN technologies.

Despite the investment uncertainty that underlined this period from the start of COVID-19 era to the start of the War in Ukraine and the latest development in 2023, the pandemic and War in Ukraine highlighted the need for renewable energy sources in Europe and GBNs. With more and more European countries including renewables in their recovery plans, technologies for harvesting solar, wind, tidal, geothermal, and other forms of energy are expected to significantly attract investments over the next few years.

6.1.8 PESTEL analysis concluding remarks

In conclusion, the deployment of innovative products and services related to GBNs is influenced by a multitude of factors, including technological, environmental, and geopolitical factors (Figure 24). However, in the current context, the most significant influences are likely to be technological and environmental factors. Technological advancements, like digitalization, 5G networks, and emerging technologies like NB-IoT, are expected to enhance the capabilities of GBN innovations. At the same time, environmental factors like climate change and environmental degradation drive the adoption of innovative products that promote sustainability and mitigate environmental impact. Moreover, the COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the need for resilient digital infrastructure and the adoption of technologies, while the War in Ukraine has created geopolitical tensions that can impact the supply chain and funding for research and development. Regarding the rest of the factors included in the analysis, Political, Legal and Economic factors are highly significant but not expected to create disrupting influences. In contrast, social influences are not expected to be of low significance in the further development and deployment of products and services to markets.

Technological factors play a vital role in deploying GBNs and related PROBONO results, as they drive the development and adoption of new and innovative products and services. The increasing prevalence of digital technologies and their integration with physical systems, as well as the development and deployment of 5G networks [110], are likely to enhance the capabilities of GBN innovations. These technological advancements are expected to enable more efficient and effective use of resources and support the growth of GBN-related applications. Technology developed in the mobility space, such as smart cities applications, and autonomous and green vehicles, are only expected to promote the adoption of GBN-related technology. Moreover, the emergence of new technologies like Narrowband IoT (NB-IoT) and Radio-Frequency Identification (RFID) can provide wider coverage, low-power on-site devices, and support smart energy management applications. These technological advancements will enable bigger volumes and more types of data to be available for analytics applications, positively impacting decision-making support outcomes of GBN projects like PROBONO. Environmental factors are the second most significant macro-level influence in the deployment of GBN innovations. Climate change, natural disasters, and environmental degradation are major concerns that drive the adoption of innovative products that promote sustainability and mitigate environmental impact. With the European Green Deal's aim to reduce net emissions of Greenhouse Gases (GHG) to zero by 2050, many actions and legislations are expected to be released, supporting

sustainable development and promoting the adoption of innovative products. The rest of the factors, mainly the economic, political and legal factors, are very important to deploying PROBONO innovations. Still, they are expected to not disrupt successful deployment in case of unexpected events.

Significance →	Very high	High	Low	Very low
Political				
Economic				
Social				
Technological				
Environmental				
Legal				

Figure 24: Macro-level influences significance, affecting the deployment of PROBONO innovative outcomes to respective markets

6.2 The Innovation Potential to Market Assessment Methodology

PROBONO's Subtask 9.1.3 examines the innovation potential to market several PROBONO innovative results based on well-established business modelling techniques (i.e., tools) with the goal of supporting project partners with the uptake of their results into the real-world markets and respective operations. An Innovation to Market Method is presented to achieve this goal, including all the necessary supporting tools to achieve this subtask's goal. On the bigger picture with the methodology followed within this subtask, two major results are aimed to be achieved: 1) a PESTEL analysis that builds up on PROBONO's D1.7 report and is focused on the commercial deployment of products/services to market and 2) a focused analysis of two PROBONO Key Innovative Results and an assessment of their potential to cover new or existing needs in new ways. As a conclusion to the current analysis, the two innovative results will be analysed according to the Market Creation Potential Indicator of the Innovation Radar's methodology (Table 22). The analysis within Task 9.1.3 will extract the innovative results from Task 9.3 and report D9.5 and will proceed on this analysis with the collaboration of the innovative outcome owners (through several feedback loops), who will have the opportunity to refine material and provide the low-level details that will make this analysis accurate and useful to them. In Table 22, one can notice the Market Creation Potential Indicator decision rules template, as it will be applied to each innovative result analysed within this section.

What is the maturity of the market targeted by the Innovation?	How will the Innovation be exploited	Who will use the Innovation?	What is the level of innovation?	What is the type of innovation?	Market Creation Potential level
e.g. Emerging or there are chances that an innovation can create it.	e.g. The innovation will be introduced as new to the market.	e.g. New customer segment 1, new customer segment 2.	Very innovative	New Product, process or service.	(5) Very high
				Significantly Improved product, process or service	(4) High
			Obviously innovative and easily appreciated advantages to customer.	New Product, process or service.	(3) Noteworthy
				Significantly Improved product, process or service	
			Innovative but could be difficult to convert customers.	New product, process or service	(2) Moderate
Significantly improved product, process or service					
Minor improvements over existing products	New or significantly improved.	(1) Minor			

Table 22: Market Creation Potential Indicator decision rules template, as it can found in the report by the EC’s Joint Research Centre [106]

The methodology (Figure 25) included in this section will lead to a solid assessment of the Innovation Potential to Market for PROBONO’s potential outcomes in the next years to come. The main characteristic is that the methodology draws from the already done work in D9.5 and is an extension of IP Management and Protection Methodology. This methodology, alongside Inlecom’s work with the market segmentation of ST9.1.2, presents a second WP-level outcome for WP9 which is the PESTEL analysis. Contributions from the business modelling activities within this methodology can potentially be also a contribution towards the exploitation management tasks.

Figure 25: Methodology for addressing Task 9.1.3 The Innovation Potential to Market

6.3 Innovation potential to market for two Key Innovative Results of PROBONO

Two Key Innovative Results have been selected for detailed analysis based on the criteria presented in D9.5's Section 3.3.4, with the ultimate goal of this subtask being to provide support towards project partners who are interested in exploring the innovative dimension of their outcomes. These Key Innovative Results are:

1. SOPREMA's Wood Fiber Insulation Material for Flat Roofs
2. CIDAUT's Advanced GBN integrated e-mobility system

The analysis of two Key Innovative Results of partners will be a great addition for:

- The innovative outcomes owner's R&D and technical development activity,
- The innovative outcomes owner's and the exploitation managers' planning work,
- The innovative outcomes owner's and the innovation manager's planning work and potential IP protection activity.

6.3.1 Innovation potential to market for SOPREMA's Wood Fiber Insulation Material for Flat Roofs

6.3.1.1 Introduction to the Green Insulation market

The need for modern cities to achieve climate neutrality has led to the increasing demand for green building materials that can be used for internal and external building insulation, offering a barrier of protection from outside elements, such as noise and bad weather. Still, and more importantly, insulation materials are required to reduce air and heat flow from the interior of a building to the exterior. Well-insulated buildings have fewer energy needs and can maintain the desired temperature during all seasons. For example, with specific insulation techniques such as green insulated roofs, a decrease in heating energy demand of up to 60% and up to 75% in cooling energy demand can be achieved in some climate areas [125].

Based on the market segmentation performed in Chapter 3 of this report, green insulation materials have great potential if one considers the market size for conventional insulation materials. Some market insights can be extracted based on reports [33], where it is estimated that, globally, wall insulation applications can be considered the most in-demand that, accounting for 47% of the overall market, followed by roof insulation applications at 37% and floor insulation at 15%. The global market size was estimated at 22.73 billion in 2015 and is expected to reach 38.69 billion by 2027, with the value demand in the EU being 8,471 million USD and is expected to reach 12,768 million by 2027. More information on the European market

for thermal insulation products was estimated to be 234.6 million m³, of which commercial and domestic buildings account for 87%. The thermal insulation market in Europe is expected to grow on an average of 2.8 % per year until 2019, raising the total demand in Europe to 269.3 million m³ [33].

Several products belong to the category of green insulation materials, such as windows, roofs, doors, sidings, and flooring, among others. They can be grouped into the materials used for the building's exterior insulation, interior insulation, or structural insulation. Based on these, several corresponding customer target groups can be identified for green insulation materials. The first group of potential customers is house owners and residential buildings who are looking to cover their insulation needs and usually are environmentally friendly. They mainly want to reduce energy costs and increase their property's value. One major customer group within the wider household owners' customer segment can be expected to be private and household owners interested in environmental sustainability. They would like not to burden it with their buying decisions further. By choosing green insulation material, they are expected to achieve similar insulation results without negatively impacting the environment by purchasing goods that have environmentally friendly production procedures and are recyclable. Additionally, and as we will discuss later on, companies that develop insulation solutions usually advertise and market their products to intermediates, such as architects and engineering consultants, who design the building and are responsible for contracting the 'applicators', the professionals responsible for installing the insulation solutions to the buildings [126].

6.3.1.2 SOPREMA's Wood Fiber Insulation Material Innovation potential

SOPREMA¹³, an international group of companies with high expertise in waterproofing and insulation, is introducing an innovation within PROBONO that aims to promote green insulation materials by developing a unique wood fibre panel for flat roofs with the necessary bio-based additives that guarantee anti-fungi properties (Figure 26). The innovation is especially focused on the wood panel's production stage, where the wood fibre has undergone a bio-based anti-fungi treatment, which adds important properties to the board regarding moisture control, fungi propagation, and waterproofing. While the bio-based anti-fungi treatment is currently partially biobased, the treatment is not based on 100% biological products yet. Despite this, this innovation is very important on a European and global level since, today, wood fibre insulation panels are produced without any additives & moisture control is a key issue in promoting wood

¹³ SOPREMA Group's website, <https://www.soprema.com/en/>

panels as alternatives to conventional plastic-based insulation materials. Moisture control is connected to waterproofing as well as other problems that currently exist for insulation materials and the wider market. Effective moisture control is vital in building design and construction, as it is associated with mold growth prevention, as well as respective structural damage and health issues. Traditional insulation materials like fibreglass, mineral wool, and polystyrene foam have the propensity to absorb moisture, which can reduce their effectiveness and potentially damage the building structure. However, biobased insulation materials are hydrophobic, meaning they can repel moisture, making them a viable solution for managing moisture in buildings.

In the case that an insulation board does not undergo anti-fungi treatment, moisture buildup can lead to fungi propagation, posing health hazards and structural damage risks, especially when organic materials like wood are present. To address this issue, SOPREMA's innovative insulation material is treated with biobased anti-fungi additives under a procedure invented by SOPREMA so that the insulation material can also prevent the growth and propagation of fungi and mold on the surface of the material (external insulation) or in the case of propagation within the building (internal insulation). Waterproofing is another critical aspect of building design and construction that protects the structure from water damage. SOPREMA's insulation material provides waterproofing capabilities as the wooden boards are treated with additives that prevent water from penetrating the insulation material, providing comprehensive insulation solutions and maintaining the building structure's integrity, as well as air quality.

Figure 26: The Pavarroof solution, utilising bio-based wooden boards as a part of the insulation material.

SOPREMA's wooden boards can serve as alternatives to mainstream foam and plastic-based insulation materials that have been mostly used over the past few decades by construction companies. Despite the fact that these novel insulation materials can cover insulation needs in

the same way as conventional materials, a paradigm shift is required in the industry so that architects, consultants and applicators shift towards green solutions. Several misconceptions exist in the market, which mainly concerns the acceptance of wood, especially in the case of a potential fire in the building. While SOPREMA's products are certified for their anti-fire properties, potential clients still use solutions they are already familiar with. Finally, another barrier to adopting green wood insulation materials is the industry's requirement for versatile products. In the case of wood insulation panels, it is common for applicators, the professionals that are responsible for the product installation, not to have the necessary skills for installation, thus resulting in wrong installation and unexpected results in the long term.

Based on interactions with SOPREMA's specialists, the main clients (i.e., the persona of the Value Proposition Canvases) for wood insulation panels are architects and engineering consultants that design the buildings at which the wood insulation panels can be installed. Such types of buildings are individual households, collective residential households, public authorities' buildings and potentially industrial buildings (mindset not yet developed in the sector). While wood panels can be installed vertically and horizontally in the interior and exterior of the building, the main constraint is that they cannot be installed in basements (extreme high-moisture environments). With all that in mind, and based on the input from SOPREMA's specialists, in Figure 27 below, one can notice the Value Proposition Canvases for SOPREMA's Innovative Green Wood Insulation panels that focus architects and engineering consultants as the key persona that ultimately decides for the use of insulation material, affecting the rest of the stakeholders in the process.

To sum up, the potential benefits SOPREMA's innovation can bring to the insulation materials market can be grouped in the following points:

1. Eco-Friendly: The wooden boards used in SOPREMA's insulation material are a sustainable and renewable resource, making it an eco-friendly insulation solution. This is especially important given the increasing demand for sustainable construction practices and materials. In the future we can also think that it could be possible to have carbon credit by using "CO2 sink" materials,
2. Moisture Control: Compared to other green insulation materials, the hydrophobic properties of the biobased insulation wood panel allow it to repel moisture effectively, which is crucial in preventing mold growth and structural damage. Additionally, it's a real value creation for the summer comfort,
3. Fungi Prevention: Compared to other green insulation materials, the biobased anti-fungi additives used in SOPREMA's insulation material prevent the growth of fungi on the wooden boards, ensuring that the insulation remains effective and safe to use,

4. Reusability & upcycling: The wooden boards treated with biobased anti-fungi additives can be reused and upcycled as boards after the lifecycle of a building or a potential renovation, in that way, reducing waste and providing a sustainable insulation solution.
5. New architectural designs: Wood as a construction material is not effective in insulation, but when used on the exterior of a building, it can enable new designs that are friendlier to the eye, enabling a 'green' design. This can be especially useful for large urban environments where concrete is used for the construction of the building, often exposed externally and internally, leading to the concrete jungle effect for our cities and human environments.

With all that in mind, a SWOT analysis is given, including Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats based on SOPREMA's Innovative Green Wood Insulation material is given in Table 23 below.

Factors	
S	Made from renewable and sustainable materials, making it an environmentally friendly option.
	Provides excellent insulation performance and can improve the energy efficiency of buildings either for winter & summer comfort.
	Hydrophobic properties help repel moisture and prevent mold growth.
	Anti-fungi treatment prevents fungal growth and improves the durability of wooden boards.
	Can be used as a standard insulation panel, making it easy to massify the use of green insulation materials.
W	This or similar solutions may be more expensive compared to traditional insulation materials.
	This or similar solutions may have limited availability and may not be as widely used as traditional insulation materials.
	This or similar novel solutions require specialised installation techniques and training.
	It cannot be installed in basements and other extreme moisture environments.
	The perception of wood as an insulation material can differ across countries and the lack of fire resistance is in the global mindset in many European countries
O	Green Wood Insulation Boards can be effectively used for thermal and acoustic insulation.
	Growing demand for sustainable and environmentally friendly building materials.
	Increasing emphasis on energy efficiency and green building practices.
	It can be installed horizontally and vertically.
T	Competition from existing insulation materials and new entrants into the market.
	Fluctuations in the availability and pricing of raw materials.
	The perception of wood as an insulation material is not yet mature in the industry, with some professionals considering it as not suitable due to the threat of fire.
	Changes in government regulations and policies related to green building and sustainability.

Table 23: SWOT Analysis for SOPREMA's Innovative Green Wood Insulation

Value Proposition Canvas

PERSONA: Building designers (architects, engineers, consultants)

Figure 27: Value Proposition Canvas for SOPREMA's Innovative Green Wood Insulation material-focused building designers (architects, engineers, consultants)

6.3.1.3 SOPREMA’s Green Wood Insulation Material Market Creation Potential

The potential to create a new market for SOPREMA's Green Wood Insulation material is considerable, given the rising demand for eco-friendly building materials (Figure 28). Biobased insulation materials are poised to capture a significant market share, and SOPREMA's innovative product can address multiple critical aspects of building design and construction, such as moisture control, fungi propagation, and waterproofing. This makes it an attractive option for homeowners and builders seeking sustainable insulation solutions that can boost energy efficiency and lower environmental impact. Additionally, the insulation material can serve as a standard panel for biobased insulation materials, which can simplify and encourage mass adoption. Therefore, the innovative insulation material can contribute to the growth of the biobased insulation market and attract a new customer base looking for eco-friendly building solutions. This PROBONO Key Innovative Result has been selected because it satisfied the novelty criteria of the IP and IPR Protection methodology and its maturity level as an innovation. While some Key Exploitable and Innovative Results are under preparation in PROBONO, SOPREMA’s wood insulation panels are ready to be applied in a real-world context. Based on this maturity, this ‘innovation potential to market’ analysis is important since SOPREMA is central to SOPREMA’s attempt to create and develop the market for its solution. As discussed, the main barrier is the perception of wood as an insulation material, despite the certifications and successful applications, this report can serve as the first point of communication with stakeholders within PROBONO and outside.

What is the maturity of the market targeted by the Innovation?	How will the Innovation be exploited	Who will use the Innovation?	What is the level of innovation?	What is the type of innovation?	Market Creation Potential level
The market of biobased insulation for flat roofs is an emerging market in Europe. SOPREMA is one of the pioneers in the Market, aiming to increase the market size, by sourcing more clients from the conventional insulations material market.	The innovation will be produced and sold by SOPREMA Business Units in Europe.	The innovation can be installed in several types of buildings. Roofers (i.e. roof-mechanics) are the ones to perform the installation. Building designers usually play an important role in deciding whether the product is included in the construction or not.	Very innovative	New Product, process or service.	(5) Very high
				Significantly Improved product, process or service	(4) High
			Obviously innovative and easily appreciated advantages to customer.	New Product, process or service. Significantly Improved product, process or service	(3) Noteworthy
			Innovative but could be difficult to convert customers.	New product, proces or service Significantly improved product, process or service	(2) Moderate
			Minor improvements over existing products	New or significantly improved.	(1) Minor

Figure 28: Market Creation Potential Indicator decision rules for SOPREMA’s Green Wood Insulation Material

6.3.2 Innovation potential to market assessment for CIDAUT's Advanced GBN integrated e-mobility system

6.3.2.1 Introduction to Green Building Neighbourhood (GBN)-Integrated Energy Management Systems

With the rise of smart Internet-Communication Technologies (ICT) systems, Internet-of-Things (IoT) sensors and newly developed battery technologies, a new opportunity has emerged for systems that can intelligently manage available energy reserves and streamline consumption. These solutions usually include bundles of products and services and fall under the category of Energy Management Systems (EMS). While there are several types of EMS focusing on different industries and sectors, they are usually specifically developed to enhance energy efficiency and minimize energy consumption in the area of application. These systems can also be seamlessly integrated with sustainable energy sources, energy storage systems, and electric vehicle charging infrastructure, thus creating a more efficient and sustainable energy ecosystem for a single building or facility (or a group of facilities) (Figure 29).

One of the major enablers of modern EMS is ICT, IoT innovations and modern networking solutions [110], which have led to the introduction of EMSs that handle multiple streams of input data, including Digital Twinning features that primarily focus on the building's energy management during its operation based on real-time data ingestion from sensors. The Digital Twin market is expanding worldwide and has multiple applications across various sectors, catering to different end-users, such as residential, commercial, public, and infrastructure buildings. The significance of Digital Twin models during the building's operational phase increases with the building's size and complexity. According to reports by MarketsAndMarkets [53], Digital Twin applications in buildings (i.e., all types) are expected to grow from 582 million USD in 2016 to 12,8 billion USD in 2025.

Finally, it is important to mention that based on the field of application and respective needs of EMSs may include other innovative features. First, the requirement for utilization of renewable energy through solar or wind power has set the need for integration between renewables and EMSs. Especially in the case of solar power, it is considered that solar radiation that hits the earth is about 1.8×10^{11} , and it is considered that PV systems have the potential to cover all the present rates of energy consumption [1]. For that reason, and because of the already growing solar Photovoltaic (PV) panels markets [8], the integration between EMS and solar panels is an emerging need. Furthermore, new energy management opportunities have emerged based on the expected adoption of EVs [127][128], which brings with it a large number of batteries that

will both need to be charged but will also temporarily store energy near the premises of a building, where energy consumption takes place. By utilizing these cars and their batteries as active energy storage units, bidirectional energy transfer can be enabled, lowering the expected load on the GBN grid, especially during peak hours. Finally, second-life batteries, which are EV batteries that can be applied for a different use after their initial lifecycle is over, can be another energy storage option at GBNs, which only adds to the energy management opportunities by EMSs.

There are several potential customer segments for EMS based on their exact features and application facility, such as commercial and office buildings, which can benefit from the system's ability to monitor and control energy usage to reduce costs and increase efficiency. Industrial facilities and manufacturing plants can also benefit from EMS to optimize energy usage and reduce waste. In addition, EMS can be used in public buildings, such as schools and hospitals, to reduce energy consumption and lower operational costs while also improving occupant comfort and safety. Hotels and resorts can also use EMS to optimise energy usage and reduce costs while providing a comfortable and sustainable environment for guests in exotic and remote locations. Finally, EMS can be applied to residential buildings, including apartment complexes and condominiums, to monitor and control energy usage, reduce waste, and improve overall building efficiency.

Figure 29: Scheme of an Energy Management System

Most importantly, residential buildings are a key customer segment for EMS solutions. Homeowners are increasingly looking for ways to reduce their energy consumption and costs, and EMS can provide them with the necessary tools and data to achieve these goals. EMS can monitor and control the energy usage of individual units within a building and provide insights into overall energy consumption patterns. By optimizing energy usage and reducing waste, homeowners can lower their energy bills and decrease their carbon footprint. Public authorities and their public buildings, such as schools or hospitals, strongly need EMS due to their large size

and energy consumption. They are also responsible for reducing their carbon footprint and meeting the sustainability goals of city neighbourhoods and districts. Finally, public buildings often have high occupancy rates and limited operational budgets, making it important to ensure optimal indoor air quality and temperature control for occupant comfort and health.

6.3.2.2 CIDAUT's Advanced GBN integrated e-mobility system Innovation potential

Within PROBONO and the Dublin LL, CIDAUT and other partners (BovLabs, BeePlanet) are planning to develop an "Advanced GBN-integrated e-mobility system" (Figure 30) as a solution that aims to increase energy efficiency for buildings by integrating mobility solutions in order to cover the energy demand of the Green Building Neighbourhoods (GBN, GBNs). The system integrates various technologies, such as renewable energy harvesting, high-efficiency energy transformation, second-life electric storage, bidirectional EV charging, and potentially artificial intelligence, with an advanced intelligent monitor control system interconnected with the GBN Digital Twin. The system is currently under development, starting with a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of 5 and an envisioned TRL of 7 at the end of the project. While the Dublin LL is still under development, CIDAUT and the rest of the partners developing the solution are examining the value of these innovative features and which of those should be prioritized.

Figure 30: Advanced GBN integrated e-mobility concept

CIDAUT's Advanced GBN integrated e-mobility system, as seen in Figure 30, is crucial in the mobility aspect as it allows for the efficient and optimized usage of electric vehicle (EV) batteries for vehicles currently in use or for sets of second-life batteries, which are being upcycled. This is achieved through bidirectional charging technology with both second-life and EV batteries, resulting in flexibility in the energy flow management between these batteries and the grid. This flexibility can be essential in maintaining energy grid stability and reliability, particularly during peak periods. Integrating renewable energy harvesting systems and high-efficiency energy transformation processes can further reduce greenhouse gas emissions and promote sustainable mobility. Additionally, the intelligent monitor control system uses artificial intelligence to improve the prediction and decision-making processes regarding energy demand and supply. In summary, the Advanced GBN integrated e-mobility system is vital in transitioning

towards cleaner and more sustainable GBNs but also mobility systems. With all that in mind, and considering the analysis included in Section 6.2, in Figure 31 and Figure 32 below, one can notice the value proposition canvases for CIDAUT's Advanced GBN integrated e-mobility system that focus on private residential house owners (Figure 31) and public authorities (Figure 32).

The innovation potential of CIDAUT's Advanced GBN-integrated e-mobility system lies in its integration of various cutting-edge technologies, including bidirectional charging with second-life and EV batteries, renewable energy harvesting systems, which, when combined, can lead to high-efficiency energy transformation processes and, in turn, lower consumption and load balancing. Aside from that main benefit, the system proposed by CIDAUT and partners in the Dublin LL can promote the use of EVs by encouraging homeowners in GBNs to purchase EVs and benefit from the cost savings of using lower-cost electricity to cover their mobility needs. CIDAUT's Advanced GBN-integrated e-mobility system is also expected to raise the Ownership Rate of Home Chargers (ORH), which is considered central to the adoption of EVs. With the ratio between publicly and private charging points being different from one European Member State to another [129], solutions like the Advanced GBN-integrated e-mobility system can play a key role in making European urban environments greener.

Based on CIDAUT's experience in past Research and Development (R&D) projects, the GBN-integrated e-mobility system will include features with potential for efficient energy management. Concepts such as bidirectional charging and second-life batteries have been examined by CIDAUT and its partners in the past, and they are implemented in the new proposed system based on experience. In that way, the GBN-integrated EMS system can provide flexibility in managing the energy flow between batteries and the grid, enabling efficient and optimized use of EV batteries. Dublin LL also examines how using AI in the system can enhance the prediction and decision-making processes, leading to better energy management and cost savings. Overall, the Advanced GBN integrated e-mobility system has the potential to advance and transform the EMS markets towards a more sustainable future by focusing on the interplay between green building and sustainable transport modes.

PERSONA: Residential buildings managers/management companies

Figure 31: Value Proposition Canvas for CIDAUT's Advanced GBN integrated e-mobility system focused on Individual residential buildings' managers as the Customer

Persona

Value Proposition Canvas

PERSONA: Public authorities/Public buildings

Figure 32: Value Proposition Canvas for CIDAUT's Advanced GBN-integrated e-mobility system focused on Public Authorities (and Public Buildings) as the Customer

Persona

To sum up, the potential benefits CIDAUT's Advanced GBN integrated e-mobility system can bring to the EMS market can be grouped in the following points:

- 1) Integrates renewable energy sources and second-life batteries with the GBN's EMS,
- 2) Enables efficient and optimised use of electric vehicle batteries currently in use,
- 3) Ensures stability and reliability of the energy grid by load balancing,
- 4) Increases Ownership Rate of Home Chargers (ORH) for EV users in the area of application, who depend less on public charging infrastructure,
- 5) Reduces greenhouse gas emissions and promotes sustainable mobility,
- 6) Enables cost savings for building managers and management companies by reducing management effort,
- 7) Improves energy efficiency of buildings,
- 8) Increases the re-use value of EV batteries in the area of application.

With all that being said, a Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) Analysis on CIDAUT's GBN-integrated e-mobility system is given in Table 24 below.

Factors	
S	Unique integration approach that integrates various energy systems and enables the efficient and optimized use of EV batteries.
	Can contribute to reducing greenhouse gas emissions and promoting sustainable mobility.
	Lower energy consumption and increased efficiency through load balancing and renewables.
	Potential for further cost savings and revenue generation through energy trading, net metering and demand response services.
W	It relies on the adoption of EVs and renewable energy sources, which may still be limited in some EU regions/markets.
	Requires significant upfront investment in infrastructure and implementation costs.
	Dependence on bidirectional charging technology may not be widely available or standardised.
	Competition from other established players in the EMS market.
O	Potential for partnerships and collaborations with other players in the energy and mobility sectors.
	Growing demand for sustainable and eco-friendly mobility solutions.
	It can be installed across different geographical settings.
	Potential integration with emerging technologies such as blockchain and artificial intelligence can bring more benefits and features to the system.

T	Regulatory and policy uncertainty in the energy and mobility sectors, including differentiations in-between countries.
	Volatility and uncertainty in the energy markets and the grid.
	Potential for cybersecurity risks and data breaches.
	Rapidly evolving technologies and competing solutions.

Table 24: SWOT Analysis for CIDAUT's Advanced GBN integrated e-mobility system

6.3.2.3 Market Creation Potential Indicator for CIDAUT's Advanced GBN-integrated e-mobility system

Based on the analysis of CIDAUT's innovative outcome, the market creation potential for the Advanced GBN-integrated e-mobility system is high due to the increasing demand for sustainable mobility solutions, the growth of the electric vehicle market, and the need for efficient and optimized energy management systems (Figure 33). The system's integration of renewable energy harvesting, and high-efficiency energy transformation processes also aligns with the growing focus on reducing greenhouse gas emissions and promoting sustainable energy practices. The system's bidirectional charging technology and flexible management of energy flow between batteries and the grid can benefit individual households and also provide benefits at the system level (energy providers and grid operators), especially during periods of high demand. Potentially, using artificial intelligence in the system's control and monitoring processes can also enhance its effectiveness in predicting and responding to energy demand and supply. Overall, the Advanced GBN integrated e-mobility system has the potential to create a significant impact on the EMS market and contribute to the transition to a cleaner and more sustainable energy future. Its expected benefits for the regional energy system and the local environment are expected to motivate local public authorities and governments to provide subsidies and incentives to citizens for the installation of such systems, which will further increase the market need for this type of innovative solutions.

What is the maturity of the market targeted by the Innovation?	How will the Innovation be exploited	Who will use the Innovation?	What is the level of innovation?	What is the type of innovation?	Market Creation Potential level
One of the key factors that shows the maturity of the market we are targeting is the actual uptake of EV registrations in Europe. In general, maturity has increased in all countries in recent years. However, the Nordics and Western Europe show the highest maturity in the uptake of EV registrations.	The innovation will be introduced first where many cars are likely to be connected at the same time (e.g. airport or a mall parking) and once users become familiar with the technology, in private parking areas.	Office and real estate owners, business entities, EV owners, grid operators and EV fleet operators.	Very innovative	New Product, process or service.	(5) Very high
				Significantly Improved product, process or service	(4) High
			Obviously innovative and easily appreciated advantages to customer.	New Product, process or service.	
				Significantly Improved product, process or service	
			Innovative but could be difficult to convert customers.	New product, process or service	(2) Moderate
				Significantly improved product, process or service	
Minor improvements over existing products	New or significantly improved.	(1) Minor			

Figure 33: Market Creation Potential Indicator decision rules for CIDAUT’s Advanced GBN integrated e-mobility system

6.4 Summary of IP and IPR protection methodologies for the GBN solutions

Several activities of Task 9.1 are connected to Task 9.3, and the IP and IPR protection methodology. The most fundamental connection comes from Subtask 9.1.3, which aims to assess the Innovation Potential to market for some PROBONO outcomes. To achieve that goal, the ST9.1.3 methodology has as its main input the innovative outcomes from the Innovations Registry of D9.5, which are then filtered and selected for this Innovation Potential to Market assessment. The selection of the two Key Innovative Results is being conducted based on the criteria presented in D9.5’s Section 3.3.4, with the ultimate goal of this subtask being to provide support towards project partners who are interested in exploring the innovative dimension of their outcomes.

The work in ST9.1.3 greatly benefits from the work done up to Month 16 of the project and D9.5 with the innovation and innovation potential activities as described in D9.5’s Section 3.1.1 under the title “Capturing innovation potential of PROBONO’s outcomes”. The innovation manager has already collected and analysed important information such as the Outcome owner’s use options, as well as the innovative outcome owner’s “Innovation Justification”, “Innovation Readiness” and “Innovation level”. Based on this already collected information and feedback loops, the

analysis in ST9.1.3 has a great head start and has reached greater depths. The analysis of two Key Innovative Results of partners will be a great addition for:

- 9) The innovative outcomes owner's R&D and technical development activity,
- 10) The innovative outcomes owner's and the exploitation managers' planning work,
- 11) The innovative outcomes owner's and the innovation manager's planning work and potential IP protection activity.

All of these streams of work may draw from the results within Task 9.1 and Subtask 9.1.3 and can build towards strong exploitation, commercialization and IP protection strategies. In the case of Task 9.3 and the work done by the Innovation manager towards IP and IPR protection through patent filing, the outputs from Task 9.1 are expected to bring an updated and more detailed description of two KIRs in the outcomes registry as well as an expected stronger engagement from the outcome owners in future activities of Task 9.3.

7 Conclusion of the Market Analysis

This deliverable D9.1 on Market Analysis related to Task 9.1 and subtasks ST9.1.1, ST9.1.2, ST9.1.3 and ST9.1.4 has looked into the market trends and future scenarios for the GBN-related technologies and solutions. This shall assist the PROBONO project partners in implementing GBN solutions in the PROBONO living labs and further support the exploitation, replication and development the sustainability strategy in WP9, specifically for Task T9.2. and serve as inputs for deliverables D9.3 and D9.4.

This deliverable aimed to develop a common understanding of the market segmentation for the technologies, solutions for the GBNs, identify the market indicators for the technological market segments, develop methodology for the market-oriented stakeholder analysis and study the innovation potential of the GBN-related solutions to the market with the help of two PROBONO cases.

The Market Analysis done in this deliverable considered several established techniques to collect, analyse and present the information. These include interviews, literature studies, market research, surveys, workshops and analysis using PESTEL, SWOT, Value Proposition Canvases, etc., presented in different chapters of this deliverable. The analysis also considered a wholistic approach and catered to the domains including technical, economic, social and environmental factors and parameters that shall support in understanding the future exploitation, replication and sustainability potential for the GBN concept and solutions. However, these will be further revised and refined catering to the specific exploitable results throughout the duration of the project. Thus, the outcomes and analysis presented in this deliverable shall serve as inputs for the further work to be undertaken in the tasks of PROBONO WP9, specifically for duration of the tasks Task 9.1 and Task 9.2 and inputs for deliverables D9.3 and D9.4 in the project.

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Annex 1 List of Innovation clusters

CLUSTER NAME	Nº MEMBERS	LOCATION
Association for innovation, business excellence, services and technology (Link)	64	Bulgaria
Smart Digital Solutions cluster (Link)	83	Lithuania
3R GREEN CLUSTER (Link)	11	Romania
Aclima- Basque Environment Cluster - Asociación Cluster de Industrias de Medio Ambiente de Euskadi (Link)	98	Spain
Active Life Cluster SportEST (Link)	38	Estonia
AEI AERTIC (Link)	87	Spain
AEI Conocimiento Asturias / Innovative Knowledge Business Association of Asturias (Link)	32	Spain
AEI CYBERSECURITY AND ADVANCED TECHNOLOGIES (Link)	66	Spain
AEI de la Infancia - Asociación de Empresas Innovadoras de la Infancia (Link)	29	Spain
Hellenic Association of Innovative Small and Medium Enterprises Innovation Greece (Link)	16	Greece
Pleiades IoT Innovation Cluster (Link)	59	Greece
Bron Innovation / Govtech Sweden (Link)	98	Sweden
Cleantech and energy Innovation Cluster (Link)	164	Italy
Green HoMe - Pole of Innovation for Sustainable Building (Link)	85	Italy
Cluster for Eco Social Innovation and Development CEDRA Split (Link)	20	Croatia
SRIP PSIDL, Strategic Research and Innovation Partnership on Smart Buildings and Home with Wood Chain (Link)	87	Slovenia
Green Tech Cluster (Link)	45	Germany
Power Electronics Cluster within ECPE e.V. (Link)	203	Germany
Sustainable Business Hub (Link)	67	Sweden
Tehnopol Greentech Cluster (Link)	33	Estonia
Transylvania Energy Cluster (Link)	40	Romania
Cluster Montagne (Link)	225	France
ICONIC Cluster (Link)	49	Romania
Blue Cluster (Link)	212	Belgium
CEEC (Link)	210	Spain
Asociatia Cluster Pro-nZEB (Link)	26	Romania
Estonian Digital Construction Cluster (Link)	53	Estonia
Lithuanian Photovoltaic Technology Cluster (Link)	38	Lithuania
Norwegian Solar Energy Cluster (Link)	123	Norway
Galician ICT Cluster (Link)	118	Spain
Green Tech Cluster Styria GmbH (Link)	233	Austria
OÖ Energiesparverband - Cleantech-Cluster Energy (Link)	132	Austria
Technology Cluster on Energy and Green Economy (DTE ² V) of the Tuscany Region (Link)	180	Italy
Venetian Cluster (Link)	814	Italy
Cluster Sofia Knowledge City (Link)	61	Bulgaria
Danube Engineering Hub (Link)	23	Romania

Energy Cluster Denmark (Link)	400	Denmark
Energy Cluster North Savo (Link)	20	Finland
Pôle SCS (Link)	311	France
Tampere Imaging Ecosystem (Link)	21	Finland
Cluster IDiA (Link)	81	Spain
Flux50 vzw (Link)	194	Belgium
Lombardy Energy Cleantech Cluster (Link)	145	Italy
TECES, Green Tech Cluster (Link)	46	Slovenia
Lublin Eco-Energy Cluster (Link)	39	Poland
Mazovia Cluster ICT (Link)	274	Poland
SINOTAIC - Silesian IoT Cluster (Link)	26	Poland
Transilvania IT Cluster (Link)	92	Romania
Cap Digital (Link)	1044	France
Habitech - Trentino Technological District SCARL SB (Link)	130	Italy
Green and Smart Technology Cluster (Link)	74	Latvia
Energy Cluster of the Valencia Region (Link)	33	Spain
Centre for Energy Technologie Cluster - Free Enterprise Association (Link)	106	Poland
Clúster Digital Catalunya (Link)	73	Spain
CONSTRUCTION CITY CLUSTER AS (Link)	87	Norway
Intelligent Solutions for Zero & Positive Energy Buildings (Link)	16	Greece
Hellenic Emerging Technologies Industry Association (Link)	66	Greece
South Catalonia ICT Cluster (Link)	76	Spain
Cleantech Cluster Lithuania (Link)	34	Lithuania
Process4Sustainability (Link)	17	Germany
COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES CLUSTER (Link)	162	Turkiye
Lower Silesian Technological Park Cluster (Link)	21	Poland
AEICE (Link)	189	Spain
Arctic Design & Development Environments Cluster, Lapland University of Applied Sciences (Link)	259	Finland
Polish Construction Cluster (Link)	321	Poland
Construction Cluster Ireland (Link)	20	Ireland
Estonian Digital Construction Cluster (Link)	53	Estonia
Eraikune - Construction Cluster of the Basque Country (Link)	128	Spain
Madrid World Capital of Engineering, Construction and Architecture (Link)	152	Spain
Cluster Eco-Bâtiment (Link)	208	France